

Effects of Substrate on the Behaviour and Welfare of Ornamental Fishes

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Author's Declaration

At no point during the registration for the degree of Master of Research has the author been enrolled or registered at any other university for an award. The chapters presented within this thesis are entirely the author's own work.

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Abstract

Most research into the welfare and behaviour of ornamental fish species has focused on conditions within the ornamental trade itself, with welfare once fishes reach their end destination of home aquaria often overlooked. Additionally, there is little documented evidence on common husbandry practices carried out by hobbyists across the UK, including the use of enrichment in aquaria. A variety of enrichment types are available to the home aquarist including physical enrichment (e.g., plants, substrate), dietary enrichment and sensory enrichment (e.g. lighting) but there has been only a small amount of research into the effects of adding enrichment to home aquaria. While some enrichment may be beneficial through increased environmental complexity stimulating the expression of natural behaviours, the addition of some types of physical structures, in particular substrate, can increase the growth of

potentially harmful bacteria. This thesis firstly reviewed current literature on fish welfare, focusing particularly on the ornamental trade and the use of environmental enrichment. The experimental component of the thesis comprised a lab study, which used simulated home aquaria to record fish behaviour in relation to four different substrate types. Simulated home aquaria containing a benthic (*Corydoras* sp.) and open water (zebrafish; *Danio rerio*) fish species were maintained for 10 weeks during which time behavioural recordings were carried out to understand the influence of substrate on fish behaviour. To further understand hobbyist practices in the UK, a survey of UK home aquarium owners was carried out to understand the most popular fish species kept, the use of different enrichment types and how fishes are cared for. In the experimental study, the type of substrate, including colour, was found to affect fish behaviour particularly following the addition of food. More effects were seen in the benthic *Corydoras* compared to zebrafish. The UK survey work indicated that the majority of participants used substrate in their home aquaria, although the most prominent reason given for use of substrate was aesthetic rather than being welfare-orientated. In conclusion, the welfare of fishes within home aquaria is still understudied, particularly when compared with research into the welfare of other companion animals. Given the prevalence of substrate use in home aquaria throughout the UK and its potential benefits for fish behaviour, there is a need to further understand the negative aspects of this enrichment type through the growth of harmful bacteria, which can cause disease and illness in both fishes and humans.

Chapter 1: A review of the behaviour and welfare of ornamental fishes kept as companion animals

Abstract

The ornamental fish trade has grown exponentially over the past few decades, due to an increase in popularity of hobbyists opting to have home aquaria. The health and behaviour of ornamental fishes, both during import/export and in their final destination of home aquaria has become a topic of interest for researchers. Increased understanding of the link between fish behaviour and welfare could help improve the overall welfare of fishes throughout the ornamental fish trade. The majority of the fishes within this trade are destined for a life in a home aquarium. At present, there is legislation in place to ensure welfare of ornamental fishes in research and aquaculture, however legislation to protect companion fish welfare is limited. Compounding clear legislation, is a lack of definition surrounding fish welfare and knowledge of how to identify and monitor reductions in fish welfare. This chapter considers whether fishes have the capacity to experience pain and why fish welfare is important. The main ways in which welfare of pet fishes can be compromised is presented, along with how these may be mitigated *via* methods such as environmental enrichment. Environmental enrichment has been suggested as a way of improving fish welfare and can be physical, sensory or dietary enrichment. However, there is conflicting research as to whether enrichment is beneficial to fish. On the one hand it can encourage natural behaviours such as foraging and facilitate the growth of beneficial bacteria, but it can also make aquaria more difficult to clean resulting in the growth of harmful bacteria and reduced water quality. Further research is required to understand the positive and negative effects of environmental enrichment in home aquaria.

Key words: behaviour, enrichment, ornamental trade, pain, substrate, welfare.

1.1 Introduction

The history of keeping ornamental fishes in home aquaria can be traced as far back as 2000 BC, where the Egyptians and Chinese kept and cared for captive fishes, and is suggested as a way of maintaining a readily available food source (Palmtag 2017). By the 1930s, many countries had begun capturing and trading ornamental fishes, with Sri Lanka being the main country associated with the trading of aquatic species for use in public and home aquaria (Lim *et al.* 2003). By 1992, the ornamental fish trade had grown significantly with imports and exports occurring across the globe. At this time the international import trade was estimated at \$247 million and the export trade at \$140 million, with five countries dominating the trade of ornamental fishes (Table 1.1, Cheong 1996).

Table 1.1: Top five countries importing and exporting the highest number of ornamental fishes in 1992, showing their exports and imports as a % of global exports (Cheong 1996).

Country	Exporting %	Country	Importing %
Singapore	32	USA	26
Hong Kong	11	Japan	17
USA	11	Germany	9
The Netherlands	7	UK	9
Germany	6	France	7

Growth of the ornamental fish trade has continued, with ornamental fishes one of the most popular companion animals globally. By 2009, around 4500 freshwater and 1450 marine species were being traded annually across the globe, with specific popular species traded mostly for use in home aquaria (Table 1.2; Roberts 2009). As of 2009, the yearly trade in ornamental fishes was estimated to be worth between \$800 million and \$30 billion, with approximately 350 million and 1.5 billion live fishes traded annually worldwide (Figure 1.1, Raja *et al.* 2019).

Table 1.2: Common groups of fishes within the ornamental fish trade (Oliver 2003).

Habitat	Family	Common Name
Marine	Pomacentridae	Damselfish, Clownfish
	Pomacanthidae	Angelfish
	Labridae	Wrasse
	Gobiidae	Gobies
	Acanthuridae	Surgeonfish
	Chaetodontidae	Butterflyfish
	Syngnathidae	Seahorses, Pipefish
Freshwater	Cyprinidae	Cyprinids
	Cichlidae	Cichlids
	Poeciliidae	Livebearers
	Loricariidae	Catfish
	Callichthyidae	Armoured Catfish
	Gasteropelecidae	Hatchetfish

Figure 1.1: Global exports (A) and imports (B) of ornamental fishes, between 2000 and 2016 (in US\$ million) (redrawn from data in Raja *et al.* 2019).

It has been suggested that the increase in trading of ornamental fishes is due to advances in fish husbandry and aquarium equipment technology, making home aquaria more appealing and manageable to the public (von Krogh *et al.* 2010). Although most home aquaria consist of freshwater species, the interest in marine

aquaria has increased, possibly due to children's movies, which depict colourful fascinating fishes (Andrews 1990). However, this increase in the ornamental trade is accompanied by concerns from animal welfare groups, governments, and the general public, due to the potential for fish welfare issues (Lim *et al.* 2003). In general, freshwater home aquarium fishes tend to be captive bred, whereas marine aquaria are reliant on wild captured fishes (Torgerson 2020). The typical ornamental fish, regardless of origin i.e., marine or freshwater will go through the same stages within the trading industry (Figure 1.2) which can lead to welfare issues (Torgerson 2020).

Figure 1.2: Typical stages of captive caught/bred ornamental fishes within the ornamental fish trade (adapted from Torgersen 2020).

At each of these different stages, a range of welfare concerns can occur, where fishes experience multiple stressors (Rubec and Cruz 2005). These experiences include (i) poor or deteriorating water quality, (ii) chemical changes in pH and temperature, which they are unable to tolerate, (iii) placement in inadequate tanks, which are too small, inhibiting their normal needs or contain other fish species that they are not compatible with and (iv) inappropriate nutrition (Torgerson 2020).

Concern for the welfare of ornamental fishes has grown as the trade has expanded. In order to address these welfare concerns, it is first necessary to understand what fish welfare is and how good welfare could be implemented in home aquaria and other areas of the trade. This review will firstly provide an introduction to whether fishes have the capacity to experience pain, with a particular focus on nociception; this is of fundamental importance to our understanding of fish welfare. The review will then focus on an introduction to fish welfare, why it is important and the basis on

which fish welfare was created and how it may be implemented. The final section of the review will target the main ways in which welfare of pet fishes can be compromised, how this might be measured and how fish welfare may be improved, *via* methods such as the use of enrichment.

1.2 Can Fish Experience Pain?

The International Association for the Study of Pain defines pain as an unpleasant sensory and/or emotional experience in the presence/absence of tissue damage (Merskey and Bogduk 1994). In the presence of tissue damage, pain is considered subjective, and an external eliciting stimulus should be avoided when defining pain. Nociceptors, receptors that respond to noxious stimuli, were first properly identified in teleosts in 2002 (Sneddon 2002) and in research that followed, it was determined that nociceptors in fishes are physiologically identical to those found in higher vertebrates such as mammals (Ashley *et al.* 2006). The main areas that transport pain information from the peripheral nerves to the brain are the spinothalamic tract and the trigeminal tract, both of which have been identified in agnathans, teleosts and elasmobranchs (Sneddon 2009). In a study of nociceptors in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) somatosensory receptors were found, comprised of mostly delta-A fibres, which detected noxious stimuli such as pressure, heat, and chemical stimulation. Also found were polymodal and mechanothermal nociceptors, similar to those found in mammals (Sneddon *et al.* 2003). However, in mammals, these nociceptors are comprised of delta-C fibres, with very few of these fibres found in the trigeminal nerve of the trout (Sneddon 2002). It has been suggested that the difference in nociceptors evolved due to an increase in risk of injury, as terrestrial vertebrates encounter different stimuli in their environment (Ashley *et al.* 2007). C-fibres in mammals allow a greater capacity for responding to chronic pain. Prolonged behavioural changes in response to noxious stimuli raises the possibility that nociceptors may become sensitive, which can cause hyperalgesia, due to intense stimulation or tissue damage, something that is also seen in mammals and birds (Gentle *et al.* 2003). Sensitisation is a peripheral inflammatory response to noxious stimulation, along with an increase in excitability in nociceptors, a response which is

dominant in human pain (Scholz and Woolf 2002). The reduced number of C-fibres found in fishes could suggest that they cannot experience pain, however, fishes show prolonged behavioural changes in response to noxious stimuli (Sneddon *et al.* 2003).

For measuring pain in humans, imaging methods can be used to determine specific areas of the brain that activate during a painful experience, which can be backed up via verbal communication. However, when using these methods in fishes, it is difficult to verify that the areas of the brain that are activated are accompanied by real time feelings of pain (Rose *et al.* 2014). In terms of interactions between humans and animals, the definition of pain has to be altered for use in scientific/research situations, due to the inability of fishes to communicate verbally. This results in what are known as operational definitions (Roques *et al.* 2010), which explain how pain is measured in a particular experiment. For example, shock therapy has been used to identify pain within fishes, determined by the avoidance behaviour fishes show in response to the shock (Rose *et al.* 2014). As a whole, pain in fishes must be observed and measured as a response, with pain thought of as the perception and aversive sensory experience in response to a noxious stimulus that causes or can potentially cause injury (Sneddon *et al.* 2003). If fishes do have the capacity to feel pain due to a noxious stimulus, then they should automatically move away from the stimulus and learn to avoid it. If this occurs then the fishes have demonstrated a behavioural change as a way of reducing further injury and pain, to prevent the injury from recurring and to allow healing and recovery (Rose *et al.* 2014).

In addition to these observable measures, neurobiological and behavioural criteria have been suggested as a way to determine whether a fish can experience pain. These criteria include relevant brain sections that have the ability to process pain and/or nociceptive stimuli, pathways from the peripheral nerves to the brain and the presence of opioid receptors (Sneddon 2009). Many studies have been carried out on multiple fish species, to try and determine whether fishes have the capacity to experience pain (Sneddon *et al.* 2003). During noxious stimulation, electrical activity has been found in the forebrain and midbrain of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus*

mykiss) and goldfish (*Carassius auratus*), which differs depending on stimulus type (simple touch, painful stimuli) (Dunlop and Laming 2005). Furthermore, opioid receptors have been identified in the brains of multiple fish species and as in mammals, which are responsible for the processing of nociception and pain information (Alvarez *et al.* 2006). Evidence from these studies combined indicate that fishes experience pain (Berlinghieri *et al.* 2021).

At present, there is still conflicting opinion on whether fishes have the ability to experience pain (Adamo 2018, Walters 2018, Sneddon 2019, Brown and Key 2021). To gain a greater understanding of whether conscious states exist in fishes, a greater knowledge of forebrain neuroanatomy is required, along with how structures within the brain influence behaviour and how they respond to environmental pressures (Chandroo, Duncan and Moccia 2004). However, irrespective of whether fishes possess the ability to experience pain, they are a living animal, so therefore should be in receipt of welfare protection, whether it be in aquaculture or within the ornamental fish trade.

1.3 Fish Welfare and Why it is Important

The welfare of an animal refers to its quality of life. This can cause disagreements amongst scientists, due to welfare being difficult to define in scientific terms and involves deriving judgements about the meaning of quality of life, something that can differ from scientist to scientist (Fraser 2009, Millman 2009). Due to this, how the concept of welfare can be applied to fishes has remained unclear and largely unexamined in the field of science, irrespective of the many human-fish interactions that occur (Chandroo, Duncan and Moccia 2004). Humans interact with fishes on a number of levels, such as fisheries, aquaculture, sports, hobbyists or in scientific research (Huntingford *et al.* 2006). Therefore, it is important to gain an understanding of what good fish welfare would look like and to be able to evaluate the needs of the fish against human interest when they are in conflict with each other

(Appleby and Sandoe 2002). Firstly, the concept of welfare in relation to animals, must be understood, to be able to see how it may be applicable to fishes.

Historically, animal welfare has focused on terrestrial animals, with little research into the welfare of fishes (Branson 2008). The approach to animal welfare was initially produced by the Farm Animal Welfare Council, which stated five freedoms for an animal to be in receipt of good welfare, they should be free from (FAWC 2009):

1. Thirst, hunger, or malnutrition
2. Discomfort (i.e., be housed appropriately)
3. Pain, injury, or disease
4. Having natural behaviours restricted
5. Fear and distress

These guidelines are a baseline to be followed for welfare of captive animals to ensure normal biological functioning, something that most scientists agree upon. Some scientists believe that these guidelines can be reworked to be applicable to fishes (Williams *et al.* 2009). The reworking of the five freedoms to be suitable to fishes, led to the creation of three approaches (Fraser 2008) which include feelings based, functioning based and natural behaviour.

The feelings-based approach was created *via* behavioural studies, which were carried out to determine whether fishes had a willingness to actively achieve a desired outcome or whether they displayed fear or avoidance towards a particular stimulus, therefore proving fishes are sentient beings (Hewson 2003). Like the five freedoms, the feelings-based approach requires that a fish should feel well, be free from negative experiences, such as pain or fear and have access to positive situations, such as companionship in social species (Arlinghaus *et al.* 2007). The functioning-based approach refers to a fish's ability to adapt to their environment, with good welfare being defined as functioning well from a biological perspective in order to adapt to their environment, without being forced beyond their natural capabilities (Huntingford *et al.* 2006). The natural behaviour-based approach is the understanding that fishes have inherited biological behaviours that must be expressed, with good welfare allowing the animal to lead a normal life and express their natural behaviours (Arlinghaus *et al.* 2007).

These three approaches have been heavily criticised by other scientists, who believe that this method of determining fish welfare has poor scientific concepts and relates human-based feelings to fish, which is not a constructive way to address fish welfare (Arlinghaus *et al.* 2007). The avoidance of feeling-based approaches does not necessarily eradicate the need for fish welfare, but instead a more scientifically robust approach could provide a different avenue, on which fish welfare could be based (Huntingford *et al.* 2006). Different countries have different welfare acts, which also pose a problem in creating a generalised fish welfare across the globe.

In terms of legislation in the UK, animal welfare concerns historically originated from farmed livestock, due to intensification of farming and increased confinement of farmed animals (Rioja-Lang *et al.* 2020). This welfare at present, is implemented via legislative standards and codes of practice, which is enforced and monitored by the State Veterinary Service, with assistance from the Farm Animal Welfare Council (Bennett *et al.* 2004). Many countries are now using animal welfare regulations to protect a wide range of animals, which could be applicable to fishes, but at present fish owners are not morally obligated to ensure good welfare of animals in their care (Berlinghieri *et al.* 2021). The Ornamental Aquatic Trade Association is a UK based organisation that aims to bring more protection for fishes, by providing education and training to aquatic retailers and customers, whilst encouraging responsible ownership for fish keepers. Through education they aim to encourage responsible fish owners to care for their pets properly, providing information on fish needs (OATA 2023). These include that fishes need a suitable tank or pond that is big enough and contains the correct accessories, they need the correct food, specific for the species. Fish also should be provided with a suitable environment in which to behave normally, the correct tank mates and protection from pain, suffering and injury. OATA have published extensive guidelines for aquatic retailers and pet shop inspectors, but very little has been published regarding hobbyists and fish husbandry (King 2019). However, with more scientific research being produced regularly, an increase in an understanding of fish behaviour has occurred, which has led to a growth in negative welfare indicators being identified.

1.4 Fish Welfare in Home Aquaria

Ensuring welfare of fishes kept in home aquaria is a complex issue, due to the high numbers of species-specific factors that must be known, considered, and monitored (Toni *et al.* 2018). In home aquaria, fish welfare can be promoted by appropriate physical and/or chemical water parameters, stocking densities and feed management (Jones *et al.* 2021). Additionally, prior to arrival in a home aquarium, there are many welfare concerns associated with the transport of ornamental fishes from their point of origin to their final destination (Table 1.3). These concerns include water quality, aquarium size, stocking density, feed management, social housing, and disease (Pleeging and Moons 2017). The following sections will look more closely at water quality, stocking density, feed management and disease in relation to welfare.

Table 1.3: Welfare concerns at different destinations ornamental fishes may encounter (adapted from Jones *et al.* 2021).

Transportation Stage	High Stocking Density	Poor Water Quality	Handling	Disease
Aquaculture	✓	✓	✓	✓
Capture			✓	✓
Transportation	✓	✓		✓
Holding Facility	✓	✓		✓
Exporter	✓	✓	✓	✓
Importer	✓	✓	✓	✓
Wholesaler	✓	✓	✓	✓
Retailer	✓	✓	✓	✓
Home Aquarium	✓	✓	✓	✓

1.4.1 Water Quality Parameters

Fishes kept in a confined volume of water, i.e., a tank, can experience a deterioration in water quality which can have disastrous consequences for fish welfare (Roberts and Palmeiro 2008). This occurs due to an increase in nitrogenous waste products such as ammonia and free carbon dioxide molecules released from the fish, which cause a reduction in dissolved oxygen, increasing stress and impacting negatively on fish welfare (Pottinger *et al.* 1992). Within a fish tank, the most important parameters to control to ensure good water quality are levels of ammonia (NH₃), nitrates (NO₃⁻), nitrites (NO₂⁻), pH, dissolved oxygen, chlorine for freshwater species and salinity for marine species (Pichavant *et al.* 2001).

Temperature in home aquaria, can also negatively impact the welfare of ornamental fishes if they are exposed to temperatures out-with their normal temperature tolerance range. The consequences of either an increase or decrease in temperature can cause changes in fish metabolism and other physiologically related functions, such as contraction of the heart. Fish are ectotherms, so their external environment is correlated with their internal environment; if the external temperature increases, then the rate of biochemical reactions within their body will also increase (Natarajan *et al.* 2009) and *vice versa*.

To manage good water quality in a home aquarium, a biological filter should be used, which encourages growth of bacteria that break down nitrogenous products *via* nitrification (Morgana and Tromborg 2007). Partial water changes should be carried out periodically to remove excess food and faeces (Pleeging and Moons 2017); the frequency of water changes required depends on the water quality. It can take around 40-60 days for a home aquarium filter to mature, i.e., for enough bacteria to accumulate to aid in maintaining good water quality. Some aquarists, therefore, choose to use biological and conditioning agents such as Microbe-Lift and Quick Start to speed up the maturation process (Demeke and Tassew 2016, Jones *et al.* 2021). In the absence of a biological filter, water changes would be required much more frequently, as there would be a faster build-up of waste products, with the increased water changes increasing disturbance to the fish. A high stocking density can also impact on the quality of water within home aquaria, as there will be an increase in excretion of waste products and excess food leading to poor welfare.

However, stocking density that is too low may also cause poor welfare, due to an increase in competition and aggression.

1.4.2 Stocking Densities and Feed Management

Advice on stocking densities varies dependent on the species being kept, with stocking densities directly affecting survival, growth, behaviour, feeding and water quality (Chambel *et al.* 2015). In general, an increase in stocking density, will cause increased stress in fishes, leading to reduced growth and feeding (de Oliveira *et al.* 2012). This increase in stress occurs through a combination of poor water quality (e.g., increased nitrogenous waste, increased oxygen consumption, increased suspended solids) and increased aggression (Chambel *et al.* 2015).

However, in some species, low stocking densities can cause an increase in territorial behaviours and aggression from dominant fish which will consistently aggressively target subordinates (Sloman and Armstrong 2002). In other species, low stocking densities can lead to a reduction in feeding, resulting in poor growth, due to sociable fish being unable to form shoals/groups (Suleiman and Solomon 2017). Therefore, identifying the optimum stocking density for specific species is essential in maintaining good fish husbandry practices (Chambel *et al.* 2015). Both poor water quality and inappropriate stocking densities have a negative impact on fish welfare in home aquaria, however, poor feed management can also negatively impact welfare.

Food and nutrition are essential for the health and survival of ornamental fishes, with the daily amount required to maintain body mass differing between species. For example, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) require less than 2.4% of their total body mass per day, whilst neon tetra (*Paracheirodon innesi*) require approximately 1.9% of their total body mass per day (Pannevis and Earle 1994). Knowing how much to feed fishes without over or underfeeding is a problem that is seen in many home aquaria, with feed amount usually based upon fish size (Masser *et al.* 1999). Distribution, feeding frequency, feed delivery and underfeeding are all situations that can cause aggression in fish, leading to poor welfare (Noble *et al.* 2007).

Overfeeding has a negative impact on fish welfare, due to interfering with water quality, while underfeeding can lead to malnutrition and competition for food (Ribeiro *et al.* 2021). Overfeeding can result in fish displaying abnormal behaviours and overall functioning, which can increase chances of mortality (Kulczykowska and Vazquez 2010). In a study on Siamese fighting fish (*Betta splendens*) it was found that providing formulated dry feed meant there was less variability in nutritional value, less risk of contamination by pathogens and reduced costs. However, it was found that the growth and reproduction rate of this species were increased, and mortality rate decreased when a diet consisting of formulated dry feed and live feed was used (Pleeging and Moons 2017).

1.4.3 Disease

Changes in water quality, impacted additionally by stocking density and poor feed management can result in changes to the microbiome within home aquaria, which can result in disease. In wild fish populations, where individuals are spread out within a wide area, infections may affect around 15% of a population within an area. However, in home aquaria, where fishes are kept in close proximity, disease can affect all of the fishes within an aquarium (Smith 1997). A wide range of bacterial, viral and fungal infections have been found in many home aquaria and can infect many species of ornamental fishes. Disease susceptibility increases in fishes that are stressed due to their immune system being lowered and disease is likely to occur in home aquaria where water quality is poor, allowing for opportunistic infections to accumulate and infect tank inhabitants (Cardoso *et al.* 2019).

1.4.3.1 Bacterial Diseases

Bacterial diseases are the most common infectious problem affecting ornamental fishes, whether they are in home aquaria, an aquatic retailer or in the wild. Most bacterial fish pathogens are natural inhabitants of the aquatic environments in which

ornamental fishes can be found and factors such as water quality, stocking density and inadequate nutrition, can increase a fish's chance of contracting a disease (Lewbart 2001). The majority of bacteria that infect ornamental fishes are gram negative bacteria, with species of *Aeromonas* (Russo, Mitchell and Yanong 2006), *Shewanella* (Pękala *et al.* 2014), *Flavobacterium* (Declercq *et al.* 2013), *Edwardsiella* (Lowry and Smith 2007) and *Vibrio* found to be the most common genera (Abd El-Gal and Mohamed 2012, Martins *et al.* 2010).

Bacterial illness can become apparent in ornamental fishes as acute symptoms, such as ulcers, holes in the skin and difficulties in swimming (Soni *et al.* 2021). The most susceptible regions for these symptoms to occur are the gills and skin (Nora and Ebrary 2010). These symptoms may then become chronic, with ulcers progressing into haemorrhagic septicaemia, a distended abdomen, and a swollen lower intestine (Cardoso *et al.* 2019). Other symptoms of bacterial illness may be peracute (very severe and short in duration), which include darkening in colour and anorexia (Roberts, Palmeiro and Weber 2009). To prevent bacterial infection, it is important to follow good fish husbandry practices including the use of appropriate filters, regular water changes, use of water conditioners, keeping excellent water quality and reducing levels of organic matter to prevent stress (Crosby *et al.* 2006).

1.4.3.2 Viral Diseases

More than 125 viruses have been identified in ornamental fishes and *via* molecular techniques, new identifications are being made on a regular basis (Cardoso *et al.* 2019). Depending on the etiological agent involved, the mortality rate of certain viruses can reach as high as 100%, with families such as Alloherpesviridae, Iridoviridae, Nodaviridae and Rhabdoviridae causing the highest rates of morbidity and mortality (Gotesman *et al.* 2013, Whittington, Becker and Dennis 2010, Yong *et al.* 2017).

Viral illness can be characterised in ornamental fishes by skin lesions, which usually occur due to a drop in temperature, allowing the virus to infect the host (Cardoso *et al.* 2019). Some pathogenic viruses such as *Cyprinid herpesvirus* (*CyHV-1*) present

in two phases, the acute phase and the recurrent phase. The acute phase affects the juvenile stage in ornamental fishes, resulting in a high mortality rate. In the recurrent phase, adult fishes have severe skin lesions and can spread the virus to other tank mates (Davison *et al.* 2013). Other viruses such as *Megalocytivirus* have been reported in many ornamental fishes and like bacterial disease and other viral diseases, can cause darkened skin, irregular swimming and skin lesions (Nolan *et al.* 2014).

As with bacterial diseases, to prevent viral disease, it is important to maintain good water quality, but also maintain a steady temperature that is suitable for the ornamental fish species being kept, to prevent viruses having the opportunity to reproduce and infect the inhabitants of the tank (Becker *et al.* 2014).

1.4.3.3. Fungal Diseases

The most common fungal infection in home aquaria is *Saprolegnia* (Torto-Alalibo *et al.* 2005). Oomycetes of the order *Saprolegnia* are found everywhere in aquatic environments and during periods of poor water quality cause infection in ornamental fishes. This disease can be characterised by white/grey lesions on the fish body or fins that resemble cotton. This species of fungi grows in organic matter and is opportunistic, highlighting that if an outbreak of this fungal infection occurs, then there is an imbalance in water parameters (van West 2006). The occurrence of white/grey lesions on ornamental fishes will depend on the species of fish and also what stage of the infection is occurring. Early lesions can be characterised by inflammation and hyperaemia of the skin, whilst further developed infection can be characterised by deep lesions, with the uncovering of muscle tissue (Iberahim, Trusch and van West 2018).

The occurrence of fungi in home aquaria is directly related to water quality. To prevent fungal disease from manifesting in aquaria, good husbandry techniques must be carried out, such as regular water changes, water testing, limiting the amount of time light is spent on and managing the amount of feed provided (Cardoso *et al.* 2019). Fungal disease can be directly related to fishes with lower immunity, so ensuring that fishes are as stress free as possible is also essential (Powell *et al.*

2015). Disease is an outcome of poor welfare within home aquaria, so to prevent disease, welfare must be monitored and improved upon where possible.

1.5 Monitoring of Fish Welfare in Home Aquaria

The monitoring of fish welfare in home aquaria can be carried out *via* visual observations (Table 4) such as observing different behaviours and changes in fish morphology (Pleeging and Moons, 2017). Behaviour has been suggested as the most prominent welfare indicator, providing a non-invasive indication of a fish's physiological and biological state (Martins *et al.* 2012). Behaviour consists of internally co-ordinated actions expressed by an individual, so is considered the first biological variable that can be affected by the environment (Levitis, Lidicker and Freund 2009). Therefore, if a fish is performing its natural behaviour, then it may be considered to be in receipt of good welfare, with the captive artificial environment providing suitable internal and external stimuli. However, if a fish performs un-natural behaviours, such as erratic swimming or increased aggression, then the artificial environment could be unfavourable and poor welfare could be considered (Huntingford, Jobling and Kadri 2012).

Using behaviour to monitor fish welfare, could provide a pathway to improve their health, nutrition, and social interactions. Furthermore, in a home aquarium setting, behaviours produced as a reaction to stress, may be easier to identify and assess, in comparison to physiological issues, such as cuts/abrasions (Kulczykowska and Vazquez, 2010).

Table 1.4: Physical and behavioural direct observations that can suggest fish welfare is being negatively affected (adapted from Huntingford *et al.* 2006).

Observation	Possible Reason	Reference
Change in colour	Photoperiods affecting epithelial pigmentation	(Veras <i>et al.</i> 2014)
Change in ventilation rate	Low dissolved oxygen	(Barton and Taylor 1996)
Change in swimming pattern	Noise pollution and vibration from aquarium filters	(Neo <i>et al.</i> 2015)
Reduced food intake	Poor water quality (high levels of ammonia, nitrate, or nitrite)	(Santos <i>et al.</i> 2010)
Change in body shape	Temperature changes, parasitic disease, under/over feeding (feed management)	(Eagderi <i>et al.</i> 2015)
Slow growth	Exposure to harmful light intensities/wavelengths and duration of exposure (photoperiods)	(Boeuf and Le Bail 1999)
Morphological abnormalities	High stocking densities, limiting normal growth	(Jha 2010)
Injury	Inadequate tank size/shape leading to intraspecific aggression, resulting in injury	(Magellan <i>et al.</i> 2011)
Disease	Immunosuppression as a result of chronic stress	(Hermesz, Nemcsók and Ábrahám, 1998)
Reduced reproduction	Infectious agents (microbial and/or parasitic fauna) can reduce reproduction as well as environmental agents (pH, salinity, oxygen)	(Eissa 2007)

In the majority of scientific research, behaviours that have been identified as the most common indicators of welfare in ornamental fishes in home aquaria are aggression, foraging and erratic swimming. Therefore, these behaviours will be looked at in more detail in this section of the review. Morphological changes that have been identified as common welfare indicators include changes in colour, damage to fins and trauma, and will also be covered in more detail here.

1.5.1 Aggression

Fishes in their natural environment can live on their own or in a group, where groups can display short or long-term aggression usually *via* a structured hierarchy system. Living in a group has certain advantages, such as enhanced foraging, defence, and predator detection, but also has disadvantages such as increased competition when resources or territories are scarce (Hoare and Krause, 2003). In home aquaria, aggression can be increased due to fish being in a confined area. Not having access to an unlimited amount of a particular food source can increase aggression in home aquaria (Brandão *et al.* 2021) and aggressive behaviours can increase if social groups are incompatible, such as placing two territorial species in the same tank and/or having too many fishes in a single tank (Martins *et al.* 2012). Behaviours such as attacking (chase, bite, wrestling) or displaying (operculum flare, colour change) are signs of aggression in fishes, which can be visibly observed and indicative of negative welfare (Jones *et al.* 2021). Aggressive behaviours may also be heightened due to abiotic factors, such as reduced water quality, so are therefore a good identifier of poor welfare.

1.5.2 Foraging

Feeding habits and nutrition are one of the most important processes when it comes to fish welfare and survival (Huntingford, Jobling and Kadri 2012). Lack of feeding or a reduction in growth are clear indicators that something is not right within the home

aquarium. Most fish food manufacturers offer instructions on their product; however, the instructions can be vague, with suggestions such as feed 2-4 times daily, with a few flakes per fish. This can lead to under or over feeding which affects water quality or induce stress within the fishes. In addition, flake feed is often generalised, so may not be suitable for certain fish species, which can lead to poor welfare (Priestly *et al.* 2006). Knowledge of the specific species being kept is therefore critical, to identify the ideal water parameters and nutritional requirements (Martins *et al.* 2011).

Foraging is generally defined as when a fish actively searches and exploits a food resource (Danchin *et al.* 2008). Foraging behaviour can include daily feed intake/feeding rate, the start time of feeding or a reluctance to start feeding, the total time spent feeding and the activation of self-feeders (Martins *et al.* 2012). In an ideal situation, a fish should be able to reach sexual maturity age, without having to exceed natural aggressive or territorial behaviour that is essential to development, in regard to feeding (Dugatkin, 2004).

Variations in foraging behaviour can include where fish utilise a food source i.e., bottom or surface of the tank and what they feed on i.e., flake, pellet, live food, with negative welfare occurring as a result of lack of knowledge about different species of fishes (Kittilsen *et al.* 2009). Knowledge of the species can be used to ensure welfare is not compromised i.e., sinking pellets for bottom feeders, floating pellets for surface feeders (Martins *et al.* 2012). Foraging behaviour can be monitored *via* direct observation, by looking for changes in feeding habits, such as a reduction in feeding, which could indicate a number of things such as poor water quality or illness. Fighting can indicate that there has not been enough food provided, so therefore competition for food has occurred (Sanchez *et al.* 2009).

1.5.3 Erratic Swimming

Swimming behaviour can be problematic when assessing fish welfare, due to whether the observer has enough knowledge to differentiate between normal swimming and erratic swimming (Jones *et al.* 2021). Different fish swimming styles have been classified as follows (Beamish, 1978):

- Sustained swimming (can maintain speed for prolonged periods >200 min)

- Prolonged swimming, but shorter in duration, that ends in fatigue (<200 min)
- Burst swimming, maintained for short period (<20 s) can include high energy and fast acceleration from resting position or baseline speed, can also include manoeuvres with increased complexity/angles

Erratic swimming can be identified by a fish consistently darting, if unusual for their species, or hitting against the tank, physical enrichment or substrate (Lear *et al.* 2018). Identifying negative welfare may occur through noting changes in speed, direction, tank utilisation, lack of swimming and shoal distance/group swimming (Wolter and Arlinghaus, 2014).

1.5.4 Morphological Observations to Determine Fish Welfare

In some ornamental fish species, chronic stress can lead to colour changes in the skin and eyes, for example, guppies (*Poecilia reticulata*) will darken their eyes when exposed to a predator, such as species of barbs that bite on guppy fins. This indication of compromised welfare is visible and can occur in home aquaria due to inappropriate fish species being kept in the same tank (Magurran and Seghers, 1991). Physical injuries, such as dorsal fin injuries and dislodged scales in ornamental fishes are other direct observations that may indicate poor welfare. Such injuries can be a direct result of aggression and fighting between fishes and can also be caused by too much or poor handling (Jones *et al.* 2021). Direct observations or morphological damage can allow identification of negative welfare, facilitating monitoring of these issues and implementations of methods to improve fish welfare.

1.6 Improving Fish Welfare in Home Aquaria

Good fish husbandry practices can produce fishes that are less stressed, less prone to injury/disease, are in better physiological condition and have better welfare (Jones *et al.* 2021). The key to improving fish welfare in home aquaria is through stress management, which can be carried out *via* feeding techniques, such as scheduled feeding. Ensuring suitable water quality is also key in maintaining a good standard of

fish welfare, which can be checked via weekly water tests and water changes, with particular attention paid to the specific species that are being kept. Additional measures like physical enrichment (e.g., shelters, plants or substrate at the bottom of the aquarium) can also improve welfare. Different types of enrichment can be specific for some species, so knowledge of the kept species is beneficial in determining appropriate types of enrichment (Masser *et al.* 1992). The final section of this review will look at how enrichment can be used to promote improved fish welfare.

1.6.1 Environmental Enrichment

In a home aquarium, fishes can experience negative welfare from a lack of physical enrichment, as physical enrichment is something they would encounter in their natural habitat. Therefore, physical enrichment can be an important way of improving welfare, by providing fishes with places to hide and a sense of control over their environment (Pleeging and Moons, 2017). Enrichment is not only restricted to the addition of physical items. Environmental enrichment in a wider sense is the deliberate addition of stimuli, used to increase the complexity of the home aquarium environment, to reduce stress and disadvantageous behaviours in fishes living in stimuli-deprived environments (Näslund and Johnsson 2014).

Enrichment is often divided into different categories, depending on the aims of the enrichment. These categories include (Williams *et al.* 2009):

- Sensory Enrichment: Addition of stimuli to stimulate sensory organs and brain
- Dietary Enrichment: Variety of foods and methods of delivering foods
- Physical Enrichment: Structural modifications/additions to the tank/substrate

1.6.1.1. Sensory Enrichment

Natural environments are full of sensory stimuli, while home aquaria tend to lack sensory enrichment, which can cause behavioural issues within fishes. The addition of sensory enrichment aims to increase sensory and cognitive ability. For example,

rearing fish larvae in darkness will affect brain growth, with the addition of visual cues increasing normal cognitive function (von Krogh *et al.* 2010). More complex environments stimulate cell proliferation and increase cognitive ability. Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) that were reared in a sensory environment, such as having the addition of an ultraviolet light, that could be dimmed and colour changed, showed increased cell proliferation in the forebrain, compared to those that were reared in a tank with a normal light (Näslund and Johnsson 2014).

Several studies have found that sensory enrichment could be effective at increasing cognitive capabilities, by increasing adaptability and learning in fishes (Santos *et al.* 2013). One sensory stimulus is the use of lights, due to light synchronising all stages of a fish's life. Light intensity and spectrum can be altered to mimic key regulators in a fish's life. These lights can be artificially controlled and altered, to maximise productivity and promote good welfare (Sanchez-Vazquez *et al.* 2019). Fishes are also subject to auditory stimuli from human activity consistently on a daily basis, with a wide range of waterborne vibrations, leading to acute and chronic noise disruption for the fish. To prevent this, researchers and aquarists have begun to isolate, or utilise sound cancelling structures to reduce negative auditory stimuli and improve fish welfare, such as specialised units with a built in foam layer which reduces vibrations and sounds from movement and water pumps that are quieter than regular filtration devices. In addition, substrate can act as a barrier to reduce noise from movement (Ladich, 2004).

1.6.1.2 Dietary Enrichment

Dietary enrichment refers to the use of certain types of food and/or the way in which food is distributed, to influence foraging behaviour (Ashley *et al.* 2007; Näslund and Johnsson 2014). A suitable dietary enrichment process considers the biological needs of the species and the life stage they are at, which can improve welfare by promoting foraging and reducing aggression between fishes. However, foraging behaviour is very complex, with many species-specific factors involved, so correct dietary enrichment can be difficult to achieve with different feeding strategies and feed amounts requiring consideration (Santos *et al.* 2013).

Flake food has been used extensively in the ornamental fish trade and is also the preferred choice of food amongst hobbyists with home aquaria. Flakes sink slowly within the tank, becoming soft enough for smaller species of fishes to feed on (Floyd 2021). However, the use of live feed has been suggested as a way of improving welfare within home aquaria. Live feed can be used as a way of stimulating foraging behaviour, allowing the fish to actively work at obtaining food (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009). Nevertheless, the use of live feed can have detrimental effects, due to an increased possibility of pathogens being brought into the home aquarium (Mocho and Pereira 2021).

1.6.1.3 Physical Enrichment

The use of structures is important in many aquatic ecosystems, with many fish species using them for foraging, spawning, shelter and to hide from predators (Morice *et al.* 2013). In home aquaria, physical enrichment can be used to reduce stress, providing refuge from human disturbance or aggression from other fishes, with fish that use shelter in the wild, utilising shelter in captivity (Santos *et al.* 2013). The addition of shelters can reduce stress levels in certain fishes, as they are used to hide from aggression or threatening stimuli. Shelters can also have a negative impact; if there are not enough of them compared to the number of fishes, then aggression can increase due to competition for shelter (Sloman *et al.* 2011). Physical enrichment can include a tank cover, stones, logs, rocks, ornaments, live plants, and plastic plants (Näslund and Johnsson 2014).

A tank cover and the use of plants have been shown to encourage positive welfare for species of fishes who prefer to be hidden or shaded. In a study of captive sticklebacks (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) when half of their tank was covered and plants were included, they opted to stay on that side of the tank, instead of the open, uncovered area of the tank. This has been suggested as an evolutionary development, as in the wild, they utilise shaded areas to avoid predation (Jones *et al.* 2019). Another study found that goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) will swim towards a strong current to reach the planted area of their tank, which suggests that they have a preference for planted areas, compared to bare areas of their tank (Jones *et al.* 2019). The addition of structural enrichment may affect fish both positively and

negatively. It may affect them positively by increasing foraging and feeding rate, due to fish feeling protected from predators in a more complex environment. It can also affect them negatively by reducing foraging rate due to more time spent sheltering and due to reduced manoeuvring space (Gustafsson *et al.* 2014).

1.6.2 The Use of Substrate as Physical Enrichment

One area of physical enrichment that is very understudied is the use of substrate at the bottom of a tank, which can come in many forms, such as sand, gravel and soil (Näslund and Johnsson 2014). The addition of a floor substrate is likely to be suited to species that interact with the bottom or live close to the bottom throughout their life such as benthic fishes (Näslund and Johnsson 2014). The addition of substrate in home aquaria can create a more natural environment for fishes, as this is what they would normally encounter in the wild (Webster and Hart 2004). Furthermore, the use of substrate can potentially improve water quality as some of the bacteria which accumulate in or on the substrate, break down nitrogenous waste products and organic matter (Smith and Gray 2011).

Research into the use of substrate as physical enrichment has produced results with some researchers identifying benefits for home aquaria and others finding it detrimental. Substrate can reduce injuries in benthic fishes which are normally found at the bottom of tanks and promote burying behaviours (Smith and Gray 2011). In a study on Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*) when substrate (sand or gravel) was added to the bottom of their tank, it caused a reduction in skin lesions, infections, and skin pigmentation (Ottesen and Strand, 1996). Other studies suggest that the abrasive nature of some substrates can cause an increase in skin damage and injury to fishes that interact with the substrate (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009).

Substrate preferences have been reported in many animals including fishes (Baumans 2005). For example, Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) have a preference when it comes to the type of substrate at the bottom of their tank, preferring sand as they are a nest building species (Maia and Volpato 2018). The addition of substrate may influence behaviour and physiology, where some behaviours may be performed

more frequently or in conjunction with certain substrate types (Waiblinger and König 2004, Sørensen, Ottesen and Hansen 2004). The more complex a fish's environment, the higher the chance of them displaying species-specific behaviours, with a reduction in the occurrence of abnormal or undesirable behaviours (Sørensen, Ottesen and Hansen 2004). This was highlighted in research by Galhardo, Correia and Oliveira (2008) where African cichlids (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) displayed a fuller and natural range of behaviours when housed in a tank with sand substrate, compared to tilapia housed in a tank with no substrate, where they displayed very little activity.

The addition of substrate has also been suggested to increase foraging behaviours, with fishes having to hunt within the substrate to access food (Arechavala- Lopez *et al.* 2021). This can be seen in goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) who are benthic foragers and feed by taking pieces of substrate into their mouths and removing meiobenthic prey. Even in the absence of food, some fishes still interact with the substrate (Galhardo, Correia and Oliveira 2008). In research by Smith and Gray (2011) they found that long after feeding had occurred, goldfish continued to forage around the substrate for a minimal amount of food left between the substrate particles, suggesting they were fulfilling a natural behavioural need, rather than hunger.

At present, the effects of substrate on fish behaviour and overall wellbeing is still a very understudied research area. Some research points towards the addition of substrate to home aquaria as beneficial for fishes as it promotes natural behaviours and positively influences the tank microbiome, to improve water quality. In contrast, other research points towards substrate being detrimental, through damage inflicted when fishes interact with it and an increase in pathogenic bacteria living within the substrate. As almost all home aquarists add substrate to their tanks, it is clear that more research is urgently required to determine whether substrate plays a beneficial or detrimental role within home aquaria.

1.7 Conclusion

Ornamental fishes are one of the most commonly kept companion animals, with billions of individual fishes traded across the globe annually. It is evident that during transport, their welfare can be negatively impacted, but upon arrival in home aquaria, it can improve as they recover from the stress of transport. However, lack of knowledge by hobbyists and lack of legislation can cause a continued reduction in welfare. Due to an increase in popularity, there is a need for an increased understanding of ornamental fish welfare to protect ornamental fishes in home aquaria. Good husbandry practices can allow home aquarium fishes to flourish in their environment, by reducing stress, allowing better physiological health and subsequently better welfare. By using direct observations, behavioural changes can be identified and used as an indication of changes in welfare. Morphological changes are also easily identifiable and can highlight welfare issues arising within a home aquarium.

In addition to maintaining appropriate water quality, diet and stocking density, there is evidence that fish welfare can be improved through the use of environmental enrichment. Sensory enrichment allows further development of the cognitive abilities of ornamental fishes using non-physical enrichment that stimulates their senses. Dietary enrichment provokes natural foraging behaviours, which can be absent due to lack of environmental stimuli. Physical enrichment allows natural behaviours to be expressed, such as hiding from predators and spawning. One physical enrichment form that is found in the majority of home aquaria, is the use of a bottom substrate. However, at present, only a small number of studies have been conducted on the advantages and disadvantages of substrate. Some results indicate that substrate can improve fish welfare by reducing injury and influencing natural behaviours for a variety of fish species. However, more research is required to determine whether substrate is in fact beneficial to welfare, or whether its addition primarily as decoration is actually causing more harm than good.

Therefore, the aim of this thesis was to further our understanding of the use and effects of home aquaria substrate on fish behaviour and welfare. This was addressed through the following two objectives:

Objective 1: In Chapter 2, simulated home aquaria were used to test the effects of different substrate types on the behaviour of a benthic (*Corydoras* sp.) and open water (*Danio rerio*) fish species.

Objective 2: In Chapter 3, a survey was carried out of fish hobbyists within the UK to determine the range of substrates added to their home aquaria and the reasons why people choose to use substrate.

Chapter 2: The effect of substrate type on the behaviour of two common ornamental fish species kept in home aquaria

Abstract

There is now increasing recognition that understanding how fish interact with home aquarium enrichment, such as substrate, could aid in improving the welfare of fishes kept as companion animals. At present, there is very little research on how substrate can affect fish behaviour within home aquaria, with the majority of research focused on welfare of fishes at different stages of the ornamental trade. The purpose of this study was to establish whether different types of substrate had an effect on fish behaviour. Simulated home aquarium tanks (30 L) were set up and assigned one of four different substrate types (sand, brown gravel, coloured gravel, control no substrate) and stocked with two fish species (four *Danio rerio* and three *Corydoras aeneus*) once tank filters had matured. Fish were fed once daily to satiation, with water quality measurements carried out weekly, prior to water changes. Behaviours were monitored for a 10-week period. Occurrence of escape response behaviours, interactions with substrate, interactions with physical enrichment, aggression and erratic movements were recorded. There was an effect of substrate on number of interactions with the substrate, foraging behaviour and interactions with physical enrichment following the addition of food. Not all behaviours were affected, highlighting a need for more research into the effects of substrate on fish behaviour.

Key words: behaviour, ornamental fishes, substrate, water quality.

2.1 Introduction

Environmental enrichment within home aquaria is vital in allowing fishes to display natural behaviours, as they would normally interact with different enrichment types in their natural habitats (Pleeging and Moons, 2017). Enrichment itself is not always restricted to physical items but can also include sensory and dietary enrichment. Promotion of natural behaviours through the addition of enrichment can decrease the occurrence of disadvantageous behaviours (e.g., aggression), reduce stress and in turn reduce the incidence of injury and disease (Näslund and Johnsson 2014).

A variety of different things can be used to physically enrich an animal's environment, the addition of substrate is well documented in mammals and birds and is an idea now being explored for fishes in captivity (De Leeuw and Ekkel 2004). In home aquaria, the presence of substrate can be considered as an important environmental feature to encourage natural and social behaviours (Galhardo *et al.* 2008). Some behaviours may be performed more frequently in conjunction with specific substrate types and physiological responses may differ depending on the substrate in which the fishes are kept (Smith 2011). In bottom dwelling fishes such as loaches (Cobitoidea) the addition of substrate may allow a wider range of behaviours to be displayed, in comparison to fish held in bare tanks, suggesting that substrate promotes typical species-specific behaviours and reduces the display of abnormal behaviours (Galhardo *et al.* 2008). Substrate itself is a broad topic, comprised of multiple different types, with different textures, colours and sizes (Dou *et al.* 2000). Substrates vary from small particles such as sand (2.5 mm), medium particles such as gravel (7 mm) and large particles, such as pebbles (33 mm) (Fischer 2000). Size and type of substrate choice for a tank can be dependent on the type of fishes being kept, for example bottom-dwelling fishes are best suited to sand substrates to avoid skin abrasions as they spend most of their time on or within the substrate, whilst fishes like goldfish require larger substrate such as large pieces of gravel or pebbles, that enable them to forage for food and prevent them from swallowing the substrate (Arndt *et al.* 2001). Colours of substrate also vary, from plain white or black, to multi-coloured, to solid colours such as red, green or blue. The colour choice of substrate can also be dependent on the fish species being kept, such as a fish that carries out colour adaptation for crypsis when they detect the

presence of a threat (Reig *et al.* 2010). However, our understanding of the effect of substrate enrichment on fishes is understudied, compared with other types of physical enrichment, and whether substrate has a positive effect on all fish species kept in captivity is unknown.

Ornamental fishes held in home aquaria tend to have bottom substrate in their tanks, whether this be for aesthetic reasons for the hobbyist or as a form of enrichment to encourage natural fish behaviour. Why people actively choose to use substrate in home aquaria is not well documented and our understanding of the effects of substrate on fish behaviour is limited. Substrate has the potential to induce foraging in some species, but also the potential to harbour pathogenic bacteria, which may in turn negatively affect fish behaviour through overall health and wellbeing (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022). There is a multitude of different substrates available commercially for the home aquarist and it seems likely that substrate type (e.g., sand or gravel) colour and particle size may affect fish behaviour.

Fish species with different lifestyles will interact with substrate in different ways and home aquaria normally consist of mixed species assemblages. The zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is a small tropical cyprinid, a popular choice for home aquaria and in its natural environment, lives in large shoals in shallow streams and slow-moving water channels. It has also become an extremely popular and important vertebrate model for behavioural research (Woodward *et al.* 2019) and possesses an extensive behavioural repertoire, which can be easily observed and quantified in a number of different test environments (Movva *et al.* 2017). For example, zebrafish will typically be found swimming in open water in the upper levels of a tank, however, when introduced to a new environment, they will dive to the bottom of the tank, before they gradually explore the upper levels. This bottom dwelling behaviour on exposure to a new environment has been compared to thigmotaxis behaviours in mammals and represents fear or anxiety-related behaviour (Blaser and Goldsteinholm 2012).

Another popular aquarium fish the bronze *Corydoras* (*Corydoras aeneus*) is a highly social neotropical species that lives in mixed groups of males, females and juveniles, with group size varying from large groups found in rivers, to small groups in shallow streams (Riley *et al.* 2019). *Corydoras* are naturally bottom dwelling fishes that prefer slow moving and shallow water and are known for their shoaling and tactile

interactions (Lambourne 1995). As a bottom dwelling species, *Corydoras* shoal in two dimensions, therefore allowing their behaviour to be visibly seen and recorded accurately (Riley *et al.* 2019). Both wild caught and captive bred individuals display tactile behavioural interactions known as nudging, which is a series of co-ordinated movements, used as a way to engage with each other. Furthermore, due to being bottom dwelling, *Corydoras* interact with tank substrate, consistently foraging, by sifting through the substrate to obtain food particles (Kittilsen *et al.* 2009).

To increase our understanding of the effects of substrate as environmental enrichment, the primary objective of this Chapter was to determine whether substrate type (regular sand, black sand, multi-coloured gravel, natural brown gravel or no substrate) affected the behaviour of an open water (zebrafish) and a bottom dwelling fish species (*Corydoras*) commonly held in home aquaria. Behaviours expressed by zebrafish (aggression, erratic movement, latency to feed, interaction with substrate) and bronze *Corydoras* (foraging and interaction with substrate, escape response and interaction with physical enrichment) were quantified in tanks with different substrates, before and after the addition of feed. It was hypothesised that aggression and erratic movement would be higher in zebrafish in bare tanks due to increased visibility of other individuals and reflections from the tank walls. It was also hypothesised that foraging and interaction with substrate would increase in *Corydoras* when gravel was present due to food falling within the gravel, making it harder to consume.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1. Experimental Animals

Bronze *Corydoras* (*Corydoras aeneus*) and zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) were obtained from 60 L tanks containing mixed stock tanks of zebrafish and *Corydoras* at UWS. The stock fish were housed at UWS for > 6 months and were originally sourced from a local ornamental fish wholesaler. Each stock tank contained a 50 W heater (Interpet or All Pond Solutions) set to 25°C and a biological filter (All Pond Solutions).

Water changes (approximately 20%) were carried out once weekly, including filter cleaning. Water conditioner (Stress Coat) was added to every stock tank, with the amount added based on manufacturer's guidelines. Stock fishes were held under natural lighting and fed Aquarian flakes and catfish pellets (API) to satiation once daily. This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland and the Mars Research Review Board.

2.2.2. Experimental Set-Up

Simulated home aquaria (30 L) were set up and randomly allocated to one of four substrate types (n=8 tanks per treatment): brown gravel (Marina, 0.5 – 1 cm in approximate diameter), coloured gravel (Pets at Home, 0.5 – 1 cm, ~Ø), a mixture of brown and black sand (Pets at Home, 0.4 cm ~Ø) or no substrate (control). A substrate depth of 2 cm was used. Each tank was then filled with approximately 25 L of charcoal filtered water from holding containers (80 L) that had previously been filled with tap water passed through a charcoal filter. Holding containers also contained a 150 W heater (Aqua One) to heat the water to 25°C. API Quick Start and API Stress Coat were added to each tank as they were filled, following manufacturer's guidelines. A heater set at 25°C (Interpet) and biological filter (All Pond Solutions) were added to each tank, along with a plastic plant and terracotta pot, for the fish to use as shelter. Tanks were left to mature for 3 weeks, with regular testing of water parameters carried out using API Test Strips and the addition of a small amount of food every few days to encourage bacteria in the filter to grow. Water parameters tested each week were temperature, dissolved oxygen tested via a probe and pH, ammonia, nitrate and nitrite tested via API test strips (Table 2.1). After 3 weeks, three *Corydoras* and four zebrafish were added to each tank, representing typical groups sizes for these species for the size of tank. The fishes were then fed Aquarian flakes and API catfish pellets once daily. Over the first week, the average mass of food that was consumed by the fish to the point of satiation was noted and then this mass of food was weighed out for each tank so that tanks received the same amount. 10% water changes were carried out once weekly, using charcoal filtered water from the storage containers and with the addition of API Stress Coat.

Table 2.1: Water parameters (mean \pm S.D) for all weeks combined by substrate type. As the API test strips provide only a visual indication of concentration which is open to interpretation, no statistical analyses were carried out on these data.

Substrate Type	Temp. (°C)	pH	Dissolved Oxygen (%)	NH ₃ (ppm)	NO ₂ ⁻ (ppm)	NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)
Brown Gravel	24.0 \pm 3.3	7.5 \pm 1.0	86.8 \pm 9.9	0.05 \pm 0.2	0.006 \pm 0.04	5.1 \pm 10.4
Coloured Gravel	24.5 \pm 1.9	7.9 \pm 0.6	87.7 \pm 3.4	0.04 \pm 0.1	0.005 \pm 0.04	5.6 \pm 11.3
Sand	24.4 \pm 1.9	7.8 \pm 0.6	88.1 \pm 3.2	0.03 \pm 0.1	0.008 \pm 0.05	4.6 \pm 9.2
Control	24.1 \pm 2.0	7.5 \pm 0.6	87.8 \pm 3.54	0.07 \pm 0.2	0.05 \pm 0.3	4.6 \pm 10.1

2.2.3 Experimental Protocol

One week after the fishes were added to the tank (week 4; Figure 2.1), each tank was filmed for 13 min prior to the addition of food and for a further 13 min following food addition using Go-Pro cameras positioned outside the tank. Due to the number of tanks, the filming each week was completed over 2 days. Water changes were always carried out 2 days prior to filming each week to ensure there was no disturbance to the fishes. Unfortunately, data from weeks 5 and 6 of filming were lost due to a technical error, therefore behavioural data collected were from weeks 7-10 (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Timeline of experiment carried out from the set-up of simulated home aquaria to the fish being returned to stock tanks.

2.2.4 Behavioural Observations

Fish behaviours (Tables 2.2 and 2.3) were scored from the video footage using BORIS (Behavioural Observation Research Interactive Software). One fish was selected and watched for a 1 min 30 s period, after which time another fish was identified and watched for the same amount of time. Recording times were based on previous studies (Jones *et al*, 2023); using a 1 min 30 s period allowed all fish in the tank to be

followed sequentially for the video time period. Observation of a fish more than once was avoided due to the low number of fishes in the tank allowing individuals to be identified through physical differences e.g., colour and size. It took a few seconds (~20 s) after following the fish to identify another; therefore, all fish could be observed within the 13 min recording. Pre- and post-feeding footage was analysed in the same way.

Darting, erratic movement and aggressive behaviours were only recorded in zebrafish (Table 2.2). The number of times each of these behaviours was performed was counted for each of the four fish in the tank were averaged to provide a number per fish in a 1.5 min period. Number of observations of escape response and foraging behaviours were only recorded in *Corydoras* (Table 2.3) and were also averaged to provide a number per fish in a 1.5 min period. Interactions with physical enrichment and with substrate were observed in both zebrafish and *Corydoras* and combined for analysis. Therefore, the number of observations of these behaviours was counted for all fish in the tank and averaged to determine the number of interactions with physical enrichment or substrate per fish in a 1.5 minute period. As the tank substrate was visible in the video footage, it was not possible to analyse the samples blind. To counter the potential for observer bias, 20% of video footage was analysed by a second person, unaware of the aims of the experiment, to calculate inter-observer reliability of the ethogram.

2.2.5 Ethogram

Table 2.2: Behaviours identified for analysis in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*).

Behaviour	Description	Relevance
Aggression	Occurrence of an aggressive behaviour (i.e. bite, chase or circling chasing behaviour) directed by one fish towards another tank mate.	Increased aggression can be attributed to poor welfare, by increasing stress levels and potential injury. An increase in aggressive behaviours has been found to be a reaction to stressors within aquaria, such as light type and stocking density (Carfagnini <i>et al.</i> 2009). Aggression is often related to protecting resources or asserting dominance (Zabegalov <i>et al.</i> 2019).
Erratic movement	Occurrence of a sharp change in direction or speed of swimming.	Erratic movements displayed by zebrafish are frequently caused by acute stressors. If acute stressors are not present, it can be a sign of chronic fear/anxiety (Kalueff <i>et al.</i> 2013).
Interaction with substrate	Number of times fish interacted with substrate (i.e., sand, coloured gravel, brown gravel) or bare tank floor.	Substrate may influence behaviours and may indicate searching for food or simple interaction with enrichment (Schroeder <i>et al.</i> 2014).
Interaction with physical enrichment	Number of times fish interacted with physical enrichment (i.e., plastic plant, terracotta pot).	Physical enrichment may influence behaviours due to increasing the complexity of the environment (Schroeder <i>et al.</i> 2014).

Table 2.3: Behaviours identified for analysis in bronze *Corydoras* (*Corydoras aeneus*).

Behaviour	Description	Relevance
Foraging	Fish swims across tank and locates food.	A reduction in foraging can be an indicator of multiple stressors impacting on welfare. Variations in foraging behaviour, include when (nocturnal/ diurnal/scheduled/random), where (bottom/surface feeders) how (scavenger/predator) and what they feed on (vegetable/animal matter), all of which can influence welfare (Kittilsen <i>et al.</i> 2009).
Interaction with substrate	Fish stops and swims downward into substrate for a prolonged period.	Substrate may influence behaviours and may indicate searching for food or simple interaction with enrichment (Schroeder <i>et al.</i> 2014).
Escape response	Fish quickly swims across tank, typically towards a shelter/hiding place.	Quickly swimming towards enrichment to gain shelter, can be considered as an escape response to a perceived threat (Riley <i>et al.</i> 2019). The more often this occurs, the higher the reduction in welfare
Interaction with physical enrichment	Number of times fish interacted with physical enrichment (i.e., plastic plant, terracotta pot)	Physical enrichment may influence behaviours due to increasing the complexity of the environment (Schroeder <i>et al.</i> 2014).

2.2.6 Data Analysis

To determine if substrate had an effect on fish behaviour, repeated measures ANOVAs were carried out using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) with substrate and time point (pre- and post-feeding) as fixed factors, and week as the repeated measure. Significant effects of factors or their interactions were further explored using post-hoc tests (LSD). Inter-observer comparisons were carried out using Pearson Correlations in SPSS. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Inter Observer Comparisons of Behavioural Scores

The comparisons of behavioural scores between the two observers showed a high correlation for each behaviour (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Average number of each behaviour performed per fish in a 13 min observation period. N=12. A = Escape response ($r=0.998$; $p<0.001$), B = Interaction with substrate ($r=0.998$; $p<0.001$), C= Foraging ($r=1$; $p<0.001$), D= Physical enrichment interactions ($r=0.998$; $p<0.001$) E= Aggression ($r=0.994$; $p<0.001$) and F=Erratic movement ($r=1$; $p<0.001$).

2.3.2. Escape Response (*Corydoras*)

There was no significant effect of week ($F_{3,156} = 2.316$, $P > 0.05$, Figure 2.3) on the escape response behaviour in *Corydoras*. Neither was there a significant effect of substrate ($F_{3,52} = 1.028$, $P = 0.338$) but there was a significant effect of feeding ($F_{1,52} = 11.231$, $P < 0.05$) where the number of escape responses performed was significantly lower post-feeding (Figure 2.3). There were no significant interactions between any of the factors ($P > 0.05$; See Appendix A for full statistical details including non-significant results).

Figure 2.3: Average number of escape behaviours performed per fish by *Corydoras* in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of the 4 weeks when filming took place as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type and feeding period.

2.3.3 Interaction with Substrate (all fish)

There was no significant effect of week ($F_{3,156} = 1.172$, $P > 0.05$, Figure 2.4) on the number of interactions with the substrate performed by zebrafish and *Corydoras* combined. Feeding had a significant effect on interactions with the substrate ($F_{1,52} = 41.931$, $P < 0.001$) which were significantly higher post-feeding (Figure 2.4). There was also a significant effect of type of substrate ($F_{3,52} = 4.320$, $P = 0.009$) with significant interactions between week and substrate ($F_{9,156} = 4.30$, $P < 0.001$) and feeding and substrate ($F_{3,52} = 4.320$, $P = 0.009$). The effect of substrate was therefore investigated further using a one-way ANOVA with LSD post-hoc by week and feeding separately. A significant post-hoc effect of substrate was found post-feeding only in weeks 7 and 10 (Figure 2.4) where interactions with the substrate were higher in the sand treatment.

Figure 2.4: Average number of interactions with substrate performed per fish for both species in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of 4 weeks as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type and feeding period. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences (one-way ANOVA, (LSD); $p < 0.05$) between substrate type within a week and feeding period where bars sharing a letter are not significantly different. Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates no significant difference.

2.3.4. Foraging (all fish)

There was no significant effect of week ($F_{3,156} = 0.640$, $P > 0.05$, Figure 2.5) or substrate ($F_{3,52} = 2.769$, $P > 0.05$) on the occurrence of foraging behaviour. There was a significant effect of feeding ($F_{1,52} = 81.068$, $P < 0.001$) where foraging unsurprisingly was higher post-feeding (Figure 2.5). There was a significant interaction between feeding and substrate ($F_{3,52} = 3.048$, $P < 0.05$) and week and feeding ($F_{3,156} = 2.908$, $P < 0.001$, see Appendix A for non-significant interaction values). The effect of substrate was investigated further (one-way ANOVA, LSD) by week and feeding separately. A significant post-hoc effect of substrate was found post-feeding in week 7 only with the least foraging behaviour seen in the control tanks (Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.5: Average number of foraging behaviours performed by fish for both species in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of 4 weeks as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type and feeding period. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences ($p < 0.05$) between substrate type within a week and feeding period where bars sharing a letter are not significantly different.

2.3.5 Interaction with Tank Enrichment (all fish)

There was a significant effect of week ($F_{3,156} = 3.439$, $P < 0.05$, Figure 2.6) on the number of times fish interacted with the environmental enrichment. There was a significant effect of substrate ($F_{3,52} = 5.135$, $P < 0.05$), feeding ($F_{1,52} = 48.821$, $P < 0.001$) and an interaction between feeding and substrate ($F_{3,52} = 2.770$, $P < 0.05$, see Appendix A for non-significant interaction values). Therefore, the effects of substrate were investigated further post-hoc (one-way ANOVA, LSD) with week and feeding considered separately. A significant post-hoc effect of substrate was found post-feeding in week 9 only (Figure 2.6) where interaction with the physical enrichment was higher in the control tanks versus both the coloured and brown gravel treatments.

Figure 2.6: Average number of observations of physical enrichment interactions performed per fish for both species in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of four weeks as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences ($p < 0.05$) between substrate type within a week and feeding period where bars sharing a letter are not significantly different. Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates no significant difference.

2.3.6 Aggression (zebrafish)

There was a significant effect of week ($F_{3,162} = 2.783$, $P < 0.05$, Figure 2.7) on aggressive behaviour and aggression was significantly higher before feeding than after ($F_{1,54} = 33.619$, $P < 0.001$). There was no significant effect of substrate ($F_{3,54} = 2.217$, $P = 0.097$). There were no significant interactions between any of the factors ($P > 0.05$; See Appendix A for full statistical analysis).

Figure 2.7: Average number of aggressive acts performed per fish by *Danio rerio* in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of the 4 weeks as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type and feeding period.

2.3.7 Erratic Movement (all fish)

There was no significant effect of week ($F_{3,156} = 1.009$, $P > 0.05$, Figure 2.8) or substrate ($F_{3,52} = 1.662$, $P = 0.195$) on erratic movement. There was a significant effect of feeding ($F_{1,52} = 36.184$, $P < 0.001$) with erratic movement lower post-feeding. There was a significant interaction between week and feeding ($F_{1,52} = 7.791$, $P < 0.05$) but no significant interactions between any of the other factors ($P > 0.05$; See Appendix A).

Figure 2.8: Average number of observations of erratic movement performed per fish for both species in a 1.5 minute observation period where data are presented for each of 4 weeks as separate panels. Black bars are pre-feeding, white bars are post-feeding. Data are means \pm SD. For substrate type, CG = coloured gravel, BG = brown gravel, C = control with no substrate and S = sand. N=8 tanks per substrate type and feeding period.

2.4 Discussion

In the present study, the effect of substrate on the behaviour of two ornamental fish species was investigated. Coloured gravel substrate had an effect on foraging in *Corydoras*, by increasing the amount of foraging that was carried out, while bare control tanks had no effect on foraging. Interactions with substrate were at their highest in *Corydoras* in tanks with sand substrate, while interactions were at their lowest in control tanks with no substrate. Interactions with physical enrichment were highest in bare control tanks post-feeding compared to tanks with coloured gravel, brown gravel, normal and black sand. Substrate had no other effects on behaviours that were examined during this study.

The behaviour most affected by substrate was foraging in *Corydoras*. Foraging was at its highest in coloured gravel tanks in week 7 after the addition of food. A reason for this may be due to the *Corydoras* having to work harder to gain access to the food supply, due to searching for food particles that had fallen between the gravel particles (Riley *et al.* 2019, Kidd and Kidd, 1999). Only coloured gravel resulted in significantly more foraging than was seen with the sand substrate, and it is possible that the coloured gravel made the food particles easier to see. Foraging was at its lowest in control tanks in week 7 after the addition of food likely because the *Corydoras* could easily access the food particles settling openly on the bare tank floor (Lambourne 1995, Koochaknejad, Ghazilou, and Ershadifar, 2022). *Corydoras* are bottom-dwelling fishes, who consistently sift over the top of substrate to gain access to food and so this increase in behaviour with gravel substrate is perhaps not surprising (Riley *et al.* 2019, Svitačová, Horký, Valchářová and Slavík, 2024). A previous study found that goldfish, prevented from reaching the bottom of a tank by the presence of a grid, continued to mouth at the grid even though it was not possible to access food at the bottom of the tank (Smith and Gray 2011).

During the study, to distinguish between foraging and substrate interactions in *Corydoras*, body behaviour was used. Stopping at a specific section of the tank and swimming downwards into the substrate was classed as foraging, whilst any other movements on top of the substrate were classed as substrate interactions, such as

swimming over the top of the substrate and exploring their environment. As zebrafish are open water fishes, they gained access to their food supply as it floated down through the water, so anytime a zebrafish swam down and came into contact with the substrate that was classed as an interaction. Interactions with substrate were at their highest in tanks with sand in weeks 7 and 10 after the addition of food. A reason for this may be due to *Corydoras* in particular carrying out a behavioural need such as sifting, due to being a bottom dwelling species. Interactions with substrate were lowest in control tanks in these weeks likely due to the absence of any bottom substrate (Riley *et al.* 2019, Assan *et al.*, 2021). Environmental enrichment, such as the addition of floor substrate, is used to promote natural behaviours, so in its absence, natural behaviours such as interacting with substrate were greatly reduced (Killen *et al.* 2013). It is unclear why this effect was only seen in weeks 7 and 10, however, this behaviour was variable, particularly post-feeding which may have masked any effects of substrate. For future studies it may be beneficial to separate out interactions with substrate according to species to see whether effects are more prominent in *Corydoras* or zebrafish. Interactions with substrate were at their highest in sand tanks in week 7 after the addition of food. A reason for this may be due to *Corydoras* carrying out a behavioural need such as sifting, due to being a bottom dwelling species (Killen *et al.* 2013).

Interactions with physical tank enrichment were affected by tank substrate in week 9, post feeding only. Tank enrichment interactions were highest in control tanks, which were significantly higher than in both the gravel treatments. A reason for the greater number of interactions with the physical enrichment in control tanks may have been due to the absence of floor substrate. If food particles landed on the only physical enrichment within the control tanks (i.e., the shelter and plastic plant), the fishes may have interacted with the physical enrichment to gain access to the food.

Furthermore, the presence of the food may have induced an exploratory behaviour within the fishes and without the substrate the fishes explored other aspects of the tank more (Kalueff *et al.* 2013, (Martins *et al.*, 2012). In the absence of substrate, the fishes may have looked for alternative stimulation through interacting with the physical enrichment whereas in the gravel tanks, fish focused more on foraging and interacting with the substrate rather than the physical enrichment. Interestingly, these

influences of substrate on foraging behaviours and interactions with the physical enrichment, were again not consistent when analysed post-hoc in separate weeks.

Escape responses in *Corydoras* and erratic movement in zebrafish were both significantly lower post-feeding in all substrate types. Aggressive behaviours in zebrafish were also found to reduce after feeding. The lower number of escape responses post feeding in *Corydoras* is likely to be because they were more interested in accessing the food. Pre-feeding interaction between conspecifics may have initiated escape responses (Pfeiffer 1997). Before food was added, aggression and erratic movement was higher in zebrafish, which may have also affected *Corydoras* behaviour. In *Corydoras* tactile interactions or a response to a threat mediate a fight or flight response which occurs involuntarily (Kimmel 1980). While zebrafish are an open water species, their increased activity pre-feeding may have elicited a greater number of escape in *Corydoras*. Aggression and erratic movement may also have reduced in zebrafish post-feeding as they were more occupied by searching for food than interacting with each other. However, previous studies have found that the addition of environmental enrichment, such as substrate or physical items i.e., plants, hides, can reduce aggression in zebrafish, possibly due to structures reducing visibility between individuals (Bass and Gerlai, 2008, Woodward, Winder and Watt 2019).

Enrichment is often used to increase the complexity of home aquaria, which potentially can facilitate the expression of natural behaviours and reduce the amount of undesirable behaviours expressed (Näslund and Johnsson, 2014, Thore, Brendonck and Pinceel, 2020, Carbia and Brown, 2019). However, substrate as a form of enrichment for fishes has received less research compared to other forms of physical enrichment (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022). For the present study, three different substrate types were used, coloured gravel, brown gravel and a mixture of black and naturally coloured sand, while control tanks had no floor substrate. Clearly the presence of bottom substrate influenced the behaviour of both the mid-water and benthic species considered here. Substrates such as sand or small gravel stones are considered to provide a less restrictive environment when it comes to foraging and overall swimming, whilst larger stones can reduce the amount of space for fishes to swim and bare tanks can cause disorientation (Greenberg, 1991). At present, there are multiple different types of substrate available to home aquarists, from different

coloured and sized gravel and sand to glass or coloured large pebbles. Furthermore, soil is becoming another popular substrate type for aquarists, due to its ability to promote the growth of real plants within an aquarium. The effect of this diversity of substrates on fish behaviour still requires further investigation (Waiblinger and König 2004, Sørensen, Ottesen and Hansen 2004). Studies using bottom-dwelling species or those that access food by sifting through substrate, such as *Geophagus*, loaches or goldfish, are likely to give a greater insight to how substrate affects fish behaviour. Additionally, very little is known about which types of substrate prove most popular with hobbyists and the reasons why hobbyists choose to add floor substrate to their home aquaria.

In this study, the addition of tank substrate was beneficial for inducing foraging behaviours, but also lowered interactions with tank enrichment. No effects were found for behaviours displayed more in open water, such as aggression and erratic movement. Further research is required to look at a greater range of species and a greater range of substrate with a particular focus on behaviours involving interaction with enrichment. Another complication from the addition of floor substrate is the effect it has on water quality within home aquaria. In a study by Vanderzwalmen *et al.* (2022) it was found that both sand and gravel increased tank pH compared to tanks with no substrate. During winter months pH was found to remain stable, but decreased significantly in the summer months, potentially due to a number of factors including temperature. In the present study, water quality was only measured to ensure that water quality was sufficient for fish health and welfare. As test strips rather than chemical analyses were used to determine water quality measurements, they were not accurate enough to carry out statistical comparisons between treatments.

The introduction of substrate provides a bigger surface area for colonisation of bacteria and fungi, for example a marine *Pseudomonas* species attached in large numbers to hydrophobic plastics, therefore, microorganisms in home aquaria will attach to structures such as substrate depending on what the substrate is made from (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022). The growth of these microorganisms can be influenced greatly by water parameters such as pH, temperature and amount of

nutrients within the water system. While bacteria are essential within aquaria to breakdown nitrogenous products, pathogenic bacteria can also be present and keeping these pathogenic bacteria under control can be significantly harder when substrate is present (Bonn *et al.* 2015). In conjunction with the current behavioural study, water samples were stored from the different substrate treatments for later analysis of water chemistry and bacterial presence as part of a larger project and represents a fruitful avenue for further research.

2.5 Conclusions

In conclusion, foraging behaviours of *Corydoras* were higher in the gravel treatments, while interactions with substrate performed by *Corydoras* and zebrafish was highest in the sand treatment. Interactions with the other physical enrichment in the tank were reduced when substrate was present. However, substrate had no effect on escape behaviours in *Corydoras* or on aggression or erratic movement in zebrafish. This indicates that substrate is most likely to affect those behaviours associated with the substrate or physical enrichment. At present, there is very little research on the different types of substrate that home aquarists use and the reasons why home aquarists add substrate to their aquaria. Understanding the popularity of different substrates and why they are chosen would help direct future research, where specific substrate types and specific fish species, based upon popularity, could be investigated to obtain a better understanding of fish behaviour in relation to tank substrate.

Chapter 3: Understanding substrate use in home aquaria by the general public

Abstract

The popularity of owning a home aquarium has increased in recent years, with fishes held as companions, to improve mental health or as a hobby. However, there has been limited scientific research into how hobbyists maintain their home aquaria and the types of enrichment that people choose to add to their aquarium and why this is done. There is increasing evidence that physical enrichment can enhance fish welfare, however the role that tank substrate has as an enrichment type for fishes is under-researched. However, substrate appears to be a popular, if not universal, addition to home aquaria. In this Chapter a survey was carried out of people keeping home aquaria in the UK, to determine the type of physical enrichment used in home aquaria, in particular the type of substrate, and people's perceptions of why it is added. In addition, the survey assessed what species of fish were kept, and fish husbandry practices of participants. A questionnaire approach was used with a mix of quantitative and qualitative questions. A total of 56 surveys were completed by fish keepers across the UK, which demonstrated that the most commonly kept aquaria were mixed species, tropical, freshwater aquaria. Most participants (98%) had substrate in their home aquaria, however, the reasons for using substrate varied. Some participants stated that the addition of substrate was for aesthetic reasons (74%), others to improve fish welfare (41%), and others to enable growth of live plants (17%). The results provide an insight into the use of substrate in home aquaria across the UK and general husbandry techniques. Given the popularity of adding substrate to home aquaria, further understanding of its benefits and disadvantages for fish welfare is required.

Key words: aesthetic, home aquaria, husbandry, questionnaire, substrate.

3.1 Introduction

Thousands of different fish species can be found in home aquaria across the globe; however, the ownership, characteristics, benefits and detriments of a home aquaria are very limited in terms of research (Kidd and Kidd 1999). The ornamental fish trade is estimated to be worth approximately £15.7 million in the UK but represents a trade that is poorly monitored (Biondo and Burki 2020). In the UK, ornamental fish retailers are legally required to provide customers with information on fish welfare, as ornamental fishes are protected by the UK Animal Welfare Bill 2006 (Saxby *et al.* 2006). Nevertheless, there are still significant concerns surrounding the welfare of fishes within the ornamental trade, with most concerns associated with the live transport of fishes. During transport, fishes can be subjected to multiple stressful experiences (Torgerson 2020) including poor water quality (e.g., changes in pH, temperature, oxygen, nitrogenous waste), inadequately sized holding tanks inhibiting normal behaviours and they additionally may not receive appropriate nutrition.

There are multiple reasons why interacting with animals is important to humans. Human-animal interactions (HAI) have been associated with a wide range of benefits, including reduced blood pressure, reduced loneliness and increased emotional support (Allen, Shykoff and Izzo 2001). Current research suggests that the general public choose to keep companion animals to improve their overall wellbeing through emotional support, company and improvements in physical health (Staats, Wallace and Anderson 2008). While this research has primarily focused on larger companion animals such as dogs and cats, research into people who keep home aquaria indicates that people view their fishes as companion animals and feel an emotional attachment to them (Langfield and James 2009). This research suggests that support and attachment may play a role in the beneficial relationship of human-fish interactions. Nevertheless, there is no evidence to suggest that fishes exhibit separation distress, so whether a true attachment bond can be formed between a human and a fish is unknown (Bowlby 1969). However, when a human views their fishes as companion animals, this may have the ability to positively influence their husbandry practices.

There are many reasons why people in the UK choose to keep home aquaria, including their benefits as companion animals. Clements *et al.* (2021) found no quantifiable benefits to people of keeping fish during the Covid-19 pandemic but presented qualitative evidence that some people believed this to be the case. During the Covid-19 pandemic, importation of ornamental fishes fluctuated, decreasing in some months due to restrictions on importations but growing once markets reopened (Figure 3.1) (OATA 2020). It can be clearly seen from Figure 3.1 that large numbers of fishes continue to be imported to the UK, however, whether good husbandry practices are used to ensure fish welfare is an understudied area of research. Significant efforts have been made to document practices for good care and husbandry for ornamental fishes (Lawrence 2007, Reed and Jennings 2011) although how well these guidelines are applied in practice is unknown, with many home aquarists caring for their aquariums based on what they feel is best (Westerfield 2007). To promote good welfare fishes should be held in a suitably sized tank, to allow them to swim freely without restriction, for example, a 60 L tank for one goldfish (OATA 2020). They must also have suitable tank companions, where neither inter- or intraspecies conflict will not occur. For example, schooling fish such as zebrafish are better held in groups than on their own (Kalueff *et al.* 2013). Furthermore, dietary requirements must be met based upon the fish species being kept *i.e.*, sinking pellets for catfish who prefer to feed at the bottom of the tank and water parameters must be kept within appropriate levels for the species of fish (OATA 2020). Water quality is something that should be regularly monitored as parameters can regularly fluctuate. The addition of tank substrate can also influence water quality (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022, Näslund and Johnson 2014, Roberts and Palmeiro 2008, Pottinger *et al.* 1992).

Figure 3.1: Imports of ornamental fishes to the UK in 2020 during the Covid 19 pandemic, with a drastic reduction in April due to lack of imports due to restrictions. Redrawn from OATA fishing for facts (2020).

The role of tank substrate in home aquarium fish welfare is understudied, with previous research finding both positives and negatives of adding substrate (Näslund and Johnson 2014). From research that is available, hobbyists appear to add bottom substrate for a variety of reasons, including aid for live plant growth, for aesthetic reasons or to improve the welfare of their fish (Meuthen *et al.* 2011). The addition of substrate in home aquaria can create a more natural environment, as fishes will encounter a wide range of substrate types in their natural environment (Webster and Hart 2004). Furthermore, the use of substrate can potentially improve water quality if it leads to the increased accumulation of bacteria which break down nitrogenous waste products and organic matter (Smith and Gray 2011). In terms of the benefits of substrate as physical enrichment, previous research has produced mixed results. Substrate can reduce injuries in fishes normally residing at the bottom of tanks and can promote natural burying behaviours in benthic fishes (Smith and Gray 2011). However, other studies have found that the abrasive nature of some substrates can cause an increase in skin damage and injury to fishes that interact with the substrate (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009).

To establish the reasons that UK home aquarists have substrate in their tanks and to find out about general husbandry, a survey was carried out. The aim of this Chapter

was to gather insight and better understanding of common husbandry practices and the use of bottom substrate by UK home aquarists. To do so, home aquarium owners across the UK were asked to complete a survey which asked a variety of questions about their home aquaria and to return a sample of substrate from their tank.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland and the Mars Research Review Board.

3.2.2 Survey Design and Procedures

This study used surveys which were sent out *via* post to participants or could be collected from pet fish retailers. Participants were asked to answer a series of questions regarding their home aquaria and then to take a small sample of their substrate and return both the survey and substrate sample to the University of the West of Scotland *via* a pre-paid postage envelope or *via* the store where they collected the survey. The questionnaire participant information sheet and advert used on social media to advertise the survey are provided in Appendix B.

Anonymised data from returned surveys were input into an Excel file and paper copies stored in a secure, locked office at UWS. Substrate samples were stored at -20°C and checked on receipt to ensure that the label number matched with the survey returned in the same envelope. Analysis of the substrate samples for microbiology forms part of another project.

3.2.3 Participants and Recruitment

Participants were recruited *via* social media (UWS Facebook, OATA Facebook), advertising in Practical Fishkeeping Magazine and *via* surveys being placed in Fishkeeper Scotland and Maidenhead Aquatics stores. The survey was actively advertised over a period of 8 months. Survey participants comprised adults (18+) from the UK who owned a home aquarium. To participate, surveys could either be picked up from the stores or participants were required to email the researchers and request a survey kit to be posted out to them. One hundred surveys were posted/placed in stores, however, only 56 were returned.

3.2.4 Data Analysis

Answers to questions from the surveys were entered into an Excel spreadsheet. For fish species listed by participants, data were grouped together primarily by family name, with some participants owning different types of fish from the same family. Information on tank size (e.g. dimensions) was used to calculate the volume of tank in litres which were then grouped into five size categories. Information on water treatment was categorised into four groups and frequency of water changes into six. Substrate descriptions were divided into three main categories which were then confirmed by visual observation of sample returned. Different classifications for fish species, tank size, water treatment and substrate descriptions were determined by participants responses as these were open-ended questions. To investigate the reasons why people added substrate to their tanks, all the answers to this question were read and three key themes identified – these were aesthetic reasons, welfare, for plant support. Where no answer was provided, this was classified as ‘unknown’. Other physical enrichment types listed were divided into categories, with seven different types identified. Information on food type and frequency of feeding were categorised into four groups. Where appropriate, the frequency of responses within individual questions were then analysed by one-factor Chi-squared analyses.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Fish Species, Water Type and Aquarium Type

Surveys were returned by 56 participants, with most participants (n=50, 94%) responding that they kept mixed species tanks. While not a fish species, snails and shrimp were included in this analysis. *Corydoras* were the most popular kept fish species (n=20) whilst mollys (*Poecilia sphenops*), rams (*Mikrogeophagus ramirezi*) and plecos (*Hypostomus plecostomus*) were the least kept fish species (n=3 participants per fish species; Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Fish groups kept by participants, where participants could report more than one fish species (n=56 total participants).

Of all returned surveys, ~98% of participants kept freshwater tanks (n=55) whilst 2% kept marine (n=1). In addition, 96% (n=54) kept a tropical aquarium and 4% (n=2) kept a cold-water aquarium. Therefore, the remainder of this results section focuses on surveys returned by people keeping freshwater tropical tanks only (96%; n=54).

3.3.2 Tank Volume

Of all returned surveys 33% (n=18) had aquariums with a tank volume of greater than 200 L. 13% of participants (n=7) had aquariums with a tank volume less than 40 L (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Tank volumes of home aquaria provided by owners of freshwater tropical aquaria (n=54 participants).

3.3.3 Water Changes

The frequency at which participants carried out a water change was significantly different from random with a greater number of participants who owned tropical freshwater aquaria, carrying out weekly water changes ($X^2=131.5$, $df=3$, $p<0.05$). The lowest number of participants said they only carried out water changes every 2 months or more, but this still equated to 9% ($n=5$) of participants (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Frequency of water changes carried out by participants in their home aquaria ($n=54$ participants).

3.3.4 Water Treatment

The majority of participants did not test the water quality of their home aquaria on a regular basis (Figure 3.5, $X^2=185.4$, $df=6$, $p<0.05$). The majority of participants either did not add chemicals to their home aquaria or used a treatment where no brand was stated ($X^2=236.2$, $df=5$, $p<0.05$; Figure 3.6). Chemicals used by participants during water changes for their home aquaria included Seachem Prime, Aquasafe and Stress Coat. Some participants also used reverse osmosis (RO) water (7%; $n=4$).

Figure 3.5: Frequency of water quality testing (n=54 participants).

Figure 3.6: Chemical types used by participants in their home aquaria, with some participants omitting the brand of chemical treatments used (n= 54 participants).

3.3.5 Substrate

The type of substrate used by participants was significantly different from random ($X^2=82.4$, $df=2$, $p<0.05$; Figure 3.7). Higher numbers of participants used gravel (n=23) and sand as a substrate (n=29) with only 3% (n=2) using soil (Figure 3.7). Some participants indicated that they had both sand and gravel 37% (n=20). All 54 participants with tropical freshwater tanks had substrate.

Figure 3.7: Substrate types used by participants. Participants could choose more than one option with some participants using multiple substrates (n=54 total participants).

3.3.6 Uses of Substrate

There were several reasons given by participants for why they used substrate in their tanks and most participants listed more than one reason. The majority of participants ($X^2=113.8$, $df=3$, $p<0.05$; 74%; $n=40$) stated they used substrate for aesthetic reasons, 41% ($n=22$) stated they had substrate in their aquarium for fish welfare, 17% ($n=9$) used substrate for plant growth and 3% ($n=2$) stated that they did not know why they had substrate in their aquarium (Figure 3.8). Some participants had more than one reason for using substrate 27 % ($n=15$).

Figure 3.8: Reasons why participants added substrate to their home aquaria. Participants could choose more than one option with some participants providing more than one reason (n=54 total participants).

3.3.7 Enrichment

The most popular enrichment types after substrate were rock and wood (77%, n=39 for both; $\chi^2=185.4$, $df=6$, $p<0.05$). Live plants (55%, n=30) were more popular than plastic plants (14%, n=8) (Figure 3.9). Some participants had more than one physical enrichment type in their aquaria 64% (n=35).

Figure 3.9: Physical enrichment items used by participants in their home aquaria, with some participants having more than one type (n=54 participants).

3.3.8 Food Type and Feeding Frequency

The majority of participants fed their fishes flake food 64% (n=35; ; $X^2=103.9$, $df=3$, $p<0.05$); pellet food was also popular (Figure 3.10a). 25% of participants (n=14) used live food. Most participants fed their fishes either once or twice per day (Figure 3.10b; $X^2=185.9$, $df=4$, $p<0.05$) although some participants only fed their fishes monthly (7%; n=4).

Figure 3.10: (a) Food types and (b) frequency of feeding used by participants in their home aquaria (n=54 participants). Some participants fed their fish more than one type of food.

3.4 Discussion

In the present study a survey was carried out to gather information on home aquaria owned by adults in the UK, with the primary aim of determining the type and reasons why people add substrate to their home aquarium. In addition, the survey aimed to consider which are the most commonly kept fish species, the levels of husbandry people use, and whether they add other physical enrichment to their tanks. The majority (96%, n=54) of participants kept freshwater mixed species tropical tanks, with *Corydoras* (37%, n=20) the most popular fish species. A reason for this may be due to the fact that there are approximately 100 varieties of *Corydoras*, which have a calm nature, often spending their time sifting through the substrate. Furthermore, as they are generally non-aggressive fish, they can share a tank with other fish species, making them ideal candidates for mixed species tanks (He *et al.* 2018).

Almost all home aquaria contain tank substrate; indeed, in the present study 100% of participants used substrate. However, research into bottom substrate as a form of enrichment is limited (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022). In this Chapter, sand was the most popular substrate used by participants (53% n=29), followed closely by gravel (44% n=23). A reason for the popularity of sand may be due to *Corydoras* being the most popular kept fish species and as a bottom-dwelling fish, sand is the most suitable substrate for them (He *et al.* 2018) and is likely recommended when the fish are purchased. In Chapter 2 of this thesis, the behaviour of *Corydoras* varied between gravel and sand, with most foraging carried out in tanks with gravel substrate, and interactions with the substrate highest in tanks with sand substrate. The reasons stated for use of substrate varied among participants, however 74% said they added substrate for aesthetic reasons. Less than 50% of participants mentioned fish welfare in their response. A study on the behaviour of cichlids in relation to substrate found that in captivity cichlids prefer sand as a substrate, just like in their natural habitat and that this positively influences their welfare, by encouraging natural behaviours such as digging (Galhardo *et al.* 2008). In an experiment investigating antipredator behaviour of two species of goby, the sand goby (*Pomatoschistus minutus*) and common goby (*Pomatoschistus microps*), the

sand goby preferred sand as a substrate to evade predators more easily, whilst the common gobby preferred mud as a substrate to evade predators more easily. When both species were placed in opposite substrates, an increase in swimming activity occurred in response to predator cues, highlighting the role substrate plays on their behaviour (Tallmark and Evans 1986). In another study, substrate choice in relation to foraging was investigated in the three spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) where sticklebacks preferred structurally complex substrates such as gravel, which increased foraging rate, compared to simple substrates such as sand (Webster and Hart 2004).

To maintain healthy fish, good water quality in home aquaria is essential, with temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH playing vital roles (Sreenath, Rahiman and Hatha 2005). In the current study, most participants (46% n=25) carried out weekly water changes to maintain healthy water parameters. Poor water quality can cause stress to the fish, and result in increased susceptibility to disease by opportunistic pathogens (Sreenath, Rahiman and Hatha 2005). Some participants (68% n=37) used chemicals during water changes, however some participants (29% n=16) did not state which type or brand of chemicals they used during the water change process. Using water conditioners such as Tap safe or other chemicals such as StressCoat® has been suggested as an aid during water changes, to allow as little disruption to the tank flora as possible, which may explain why such a high number of participants use water conditioners in their home aquaria. However, the effects of water conditioners are under-researched. In a study carried out on the effects of StressCoat® during the transport of two ornamental fish species, guppies (*Poecilia reticulata*) and platys (*Xiphophorus variatus*) it was found that StressCoat® reduced levels of erratic swimming and aggression post-transport, however had no effect on water quality parameters (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2020). In another study it was found that adding StressCoat® prior to netting goldfish resulted in lower cortisol levels being released after being netted by the goldfish (Snellgrove *et al.* 2007).

Environmental enrichment, such as structural enrichment in home aquaria is generally considered as positive in terms of fish welfare (Näslund and Johnson

2014). Structural enrichment can include shelters, rocks and plants, which can provide a safe space for fish to hide during conflict and stressful episodes (Thore, Brendonck and Pinceel 2020). The most popular structural enrichment items used by participants were rock (77% n=39), wood (77% n=39) and live plants (55% n=30). A reason for this may be due to aquarists having mixed species tanks, so they used structural enrichment to provide refuge for their fishes. The use of structures is important in many aquatic ecosystems, with many fish species using them for foraging, spawning, shelter and to hide from predators (Morice *et al.* 2013). In a study by Saxby *et al.* (2010) it was found that group size in mixed species assemblages affected behaviour. Neon tetras (*Paracheirodon innesi*) and white cloud mountain minnows (*Tanichthys albonubes*) displayed reduced levels of darting and aggression in larger groups, which is likely to be due to a higher number of individuals encouraging shoaling (Santos *et al.* 2013). However, Saxby *et al.* (2010) found that when physical enrichment was present, angelfish showed an increase in aggressive behaviours, due to resource guarding and a need to maintain social position, within the mixed species tank. In home aquaria, physical enrichment can be used to reduce environmental stressors, such as aggression from other fish, with fish who use shelter in the wild, utilising shelter in captivity (Santos *et al.* 2013).

In the survey carried out in this Chapter, flake food was the most popular type of feed used by participants (64% n=35). Flake food is sold extensively in the ornamental fish trade and is the preferred choice of food amongst hobbyists with home aquariums (OATA 2020). The advantage of flake food is that it sinks slowly once added to the tank, absorbing water and becoming soft enough for smaller species of fishes to feed on (Floyd 2021). Some participants (25% n=14) chose to feed their fishes live food, which has also been suggested as a way of improving fish welfare within home aquaria. Live feed can stimulate foraging behaviour, allowing the fish to actively work at obtaining food (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009). Using diet as a way of enriching a fish's environment must consider the biological needs of the species and the life stage they are at. Correct use of dietary enrichment can improve welfare by promoting foraging and reducing aggression between fish. Whether participants in the current study added live feed for enrichment purposes is unknown. Furthermore, live food has the potential to introduce pathogens and

continuously varying food type for the fishes can reduce overall feeding (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009). *Daphnia*, a commonly used live food for fishes, can be infected by fungal diseases such as *Metschnikowia bicuspidata*, which once eaten and excreted by the fish, allows the fungal spores to grow within the water column, and infect other fishes within the aquarium (Strauss *et al.* 2016).

Nearly half of participants fed their fishes daily (46% n=25) while others chose to feed twice daily (25% n=14); whether this was based upon dietary requirements of specific fish species is unknown. The implications of adding too much food include an increase of nitrogenous compounds such as ammonia, due to the breakdown of uneaten food (Kasprzak, Grzeszkiewicz and Gorecka 2021). Furthermore, the results from this Chapter suggest that the majority of people do not regularly test their water, most use substrate which is likely to make tanks harder to clean, and frequency of water changes was quite variable. All these factors could lead to deterioration in water quality. To maintain a healthy aquarium, regular water changes must be carried out, to alter microbial load diversity (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022) especially when excess food is being added to an aquarium.

In this study, every participant added substrate to their tanks, with a majority doing so for aesthetic reasons. The majority of participants did not test the water quality routinely. Some participants fed their fishes twice a day, which along with no water quality testing or regular water changes, gives potential for the substrate to harbour waste products, allowing a build-up of pathogenic bacteria. Over 50% of participants had live plants within their aquarium and 25% fed their fishes a diet of live food, which allows an additional opportunity for pathogens to enter the water system and be housed within the substrate. Due to this, there is an increase in interest amongst the scientific community and fish hobbyists to understand the advantages and disadvantages of having substrate in an aquarium, along with other types of physical enrichment (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2022).

In this Chapter, sample size was lower than originally hoped, with only 50% of surveys being returned, i.e. only 54 returned, when over 100 surveys were sent out. Furthermore, as questions were open-ended, some participants chose not to further develop their answers, for example, some participants chose not to disclose why they did or did not carry out frequent water changes in their home aquarium. In

addition, some participants answered that they had physical enrichment within their aquarium, but did not explain the types of physical enrichment they had, or their reasons for including it within their tanks. A higher return of surveys may have altered the outcome of the study or at least provided more confidence in the results. Our understanding of home aquaria and the knowledge and care that hobbyists have is still very minimal and remains a key topic for future research.

3.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this survey of UK home aquarium owners demonstrated that overall, most people kept mixed species, freshwater tropical tanks and added substrate to their aquarium. Most participants added substrate for aesthetic reasons, although some participants mentioned other reasons, such as fish welfare or growth of plants. Some participants carried out regular water changes and used chemicals during the water changes, however, some participants opted to not use chemicals or carry out regular water changes. All but one participant had other types of enrichment within their home aquaria, however, the reasons behind this were not investigated. The most popular food type used by participants was flake food, with participants feeding daily, twice daily, weekly or never feeding their aquarium. Further research is required to determine both the beneficial and detrimental effects of substrate. The importance of water testing and the use of chemicals also presents an interesting area for future research.

Chapter 4: Overall Conclusions

The global ornamental fish trade is a billion dollar industry, estimated to be worth between 15 and 20 billion dollars per year (Jones *et al.* 2020). This trade is dominated by freshwater ornamental species (>2000 species), making up approximately 90% of the market, with the remaining 10% made up of marine species (<2500 species) (King 2019). The increasing popularity of the ornamental fish trade is likely due to improvements in fish husbandry and aquarium technology, making keeping a home aquaria more appealing to the general public (von Krogh *et al.* 2010). However, this growth in the ornamental fish trade has raised concern from animal welfare groups, activists and governments across the globe through potential compromised welfare issues (Lim *et al.* 2003).

The use of environmental enrichment has been suggested as a way of improving ornamental fish welfare within home aquaria (Masser *et al.* 1992). Physical enrichment has been studied previously as a way of improving fish welfare, through increased complexity leading to a reduction in stress-related behaviours, compared to fishes living in stimuli-deprived environments (Näslund and Johnsson 2014). Physical enrichment can include a tank cover, stones, logs, rocks, ornaments, live plants, and plastic plants (Näslund and Johnsson 2014). A tank cover and the use of plants have been shown to encourage positive welfare for species of fishes who prefer to be hidden or shaded. In a study of captive sticklebacks (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) when half of their tank was covered with a tank cover and included plants, they opted to stay on that side of the tank, instead of the open, uncovered area of the tank (Jones *et al.* 2019). However, a form of physical enrichment that is particularly understudied is the use of tank substrate. Nevertheless, anecdotal

evidence suggests that the majority of home aquarium owners use substrate as a form of enrichment. Therefore, the aim of this thesis was to increase our understanding of whether and why UK home aquarium owners use substrate, and the effects of substrate on home aquarium fish behaviour and welfare.

A review of the literature in Chapter 1, highlighted that the vast majority of research on environmental enrichment in fishes, did not consider the use of substrate, instead it focused more on other types of physical enrichment such as shelters, hides and plants. Of the research that was available, it was clear that the use of substrate as a form of physical enrichment produced conflicting results, with some authors suggesting it had a positive influence on fish welfare. For example, a study found that Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) had a preference when it came to the type of substrate at the bottom of their tank (Maia and Volpato 2018). Furthermore, substrate has been shown to reduce injuries in fish which are normally found at the bottom of tanks and promote burying behaviours in benthic fish (Smith and Gray 2011). In a study on Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*) the addition of substrate (sand or gravel) to the bottom of their tank caused a reduction in skin lesions, infections, and skin pigmentation (Ottesen and Strand, 1996). Other research found that substrate was detrimental, causing damage to fishes that interact with it (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009). Substrate can also increase tank bacteria which could lead to an increase in pathogenic micro-organisms and disease in home aquaria (Williams, Redman and Owen 2009). Overall, the effects of substrate on fish behaviour and wellbeing was found to be under-researched.

Following on from the review of the literature, this thesis aimed to gain further insight into the role substrate plays within home aquaria, and whether it promotes positive welfare or causes detrimental effects. In the behavioural study in Chapter 2, it was found that substrate only influenced behaviours that involved interactions with the substrate. Three different substrate types were used, coloured gravel, brown gravel and a mixture of black and naturally coloured sand. Control tanks had no floor substrate. Substrates such as sand or small gravel stones are considered to provide a less restrictive environment when it comes to foraging and overall swimming, whilst

larger stones can reduce the amount of space for fishes to swim and bare tanks can cause disorientation (Johnson *et al.* 2019). The substrates chosen here were in line with those identified in Chapter 3 as used by the general hobbyist. The presence of bottom substrate influenced the behaviour of both the mid-water (*Danio rerio*) and benthic species (*Corydoras aeneus*) considered here. The presence of gravel caused an increase in foraging behaviours within *Corydoras* likely due to having to work harder to access the food, similar to results found in previous studies (Smith and Gray 2011). In tanks with sand, interactions with the substrate were at their highest level, probably as *Corydoras* are bottom dwelling fish who consistently sift through substrate in an attempt to gain access to food (Riley *et al.* 2019). Interactions with substrate were lowest in control tanks likely due to the absence of any bottom substrate.

Environmental enrichment, such as the addition of floor substrate, is used to promote natural behaviours, so in its absence, natural behaviours such as interacting with substrate can be greatly reduced (Killen *et al.* 2013). In the absence of substrate in Chapter 2, the number of interactions with other types of physical enrichment increased. Therefore, it is possible that the presence of alternative types of enrichment may compensate for the absence of substrate. If food particles landed on other physical enrichment (i.e., the shelter and plastic plant), this may have induced interaction with the enrichment. The presence of the food may also have induced exploratory behaviour within the fishes and without the substrate the fishes explored other aspects of the tank more. In the absence of substrate, the fishes may have looked for alternative stimulation through interacting with other physical enrichment whereas in the gravel tanks, fish focused more on foraging and interacting with the substrate rather than the physical enrichment. This was also shown in a study by Meuthen *et al.* (2011), where West African dwarf cichlids (*Pelvicachromis taeniatus*) showed higher activity levels in the presence of substrate than in its absence.

Substrate was found to have no effect on escape responses, aggression or erratic movement which was surprising, as in the absence of substrate there appeared to be more tactile interactions between *Corydoras*. A reduction in tactile interactions

due to the presence of substrate could be hypothesised to reduce erratic movements as tactile interactions are known to cause an involuntary fight-or-flight response (Kimmel 1980). This finding also conflicts with other research, as previous studies have found that the addition of environmental enrichment, such as substrate or physical items i.e., plants, hides, can reduce aggression in zebrafish, possibly due to structures reducing visibility between individuals (Woodward, Winder and Watt 2019). There was no evidence of this within this study, although substrate is unlikely to influence visual contact between fishes. A study on the behaviour of cichlids in relation to substrate found that in captivity cichlids prefer sand as a substrate, just like in their natural habitat and that this positively influences their welfare, by encouraging natural behaviours such as digging (Galhardo *et al.* 2008). In an experiment investigating antipredator behaviour of two species of goby, the sand goby (*Pomatoschistus minutus*) and common goby (*Pomatoschistus microps*), the sand goby preferred sand as a substrate to evade predators more easily, whilst the common goby preferred mud as a substrate for avoiding predators. When both species were placed on opposite substrates, an increase in swimming activity occurred in response to predator cues, highlighting the role substrate plays on their behaviour (Tallmark and Evans 1986). Given that some potential benefits of substrate addition in terms of stimulating natural behaviours were seen in Chapter 2 in support of work done in other fish species, future work is needed to understand the influence of these substrate types on water quality and the tank microbiome.

In Chapter 3, all except two participants kept freshwater tropical aquariums, which is in line with the popularity of tropical freshwater *versus* marine fish, previously reviewed in Chapter 1. *Corydoras* were the most kept fish species by the participants, and represented the benthic species chosen in Chapter 2 as they have behaviours that are easily observed. *Corydoras* are generally non-aggressive fish, have a wide range of observable behaviours. They are popular as they can share a tank with other fish species, making them ideal candidates for mixed species tanks (He *et al.* 2018). Within Chapter 3, all participants included substrate within their tanks, however, three quarters of participants used substrate primarily for aesthetic reasons, not for the benefit of the fishes, with the other participants stating its use for fish welfare. As discussed above and shown in Chapter 2, there are likely to be

benefits of substrate for fish welfare although this may be species specific. The potential of substrate to enhance welfare, however, does not seem to be a primary reason for using substrate by UK fishkeepers. In addition to substrate, all participants in Chapter 3 had some form of environmental enrichment in their tanks, including rocks, wood, shelter and plants. The use of structures is important in many aquatic ecosystems, with many fish species using them for foraging, spawning, shelter and to hide from predators (Morice *et al.* 2013). Structural enrichment is generally considered as positive for fishes (Näslund and Johnson 2014) and can provide a safe space for fish to hide during conflict (Thore, Brendonck and Pinceel 2020).

Less than half of participants in Chapter 3 carried out water testing, which highlights the potential for poor water quality and compromised welfare within their home aquaria. Good water quality is of primary importance in maintaining good fish health. Poor water quality can cause stress to the fish, and result in increased susceptibility to disease by opportunistic pathogens (Sreenath, Rahiman and Hatha 2005). However, no further questions were included for participants to explain why they chose whether or not to carry out regular water testing. This would be an interesting area to explore, to understand whether this is a lack of awareness of the need for good water quality, a lack of understanding of how to test the water quality, or the cost of consumables for testing. A couple of participants did provide additional information on why they carry out water changes and use chemicals when doing so, which was to reduce disease in their tanks and to maintain the tank's aesthetic. Using water conditioners such as Tap safe or StressCoat® has been suggested as an aid during water changes, to allow as little disruption to the tank flora as possible. This may explain why such a high number of participants use water conditioners in their home aquaria. However, the effects of water conditioners are under-researched. In a study carried out on the effects of StressCoat® during the transport of two ornamental fish species, guppies (*Poecilia reticulata*) and platys (*Xiphophorus variatus*) it was found that StressCoat® reduced levels of erratic swimming and aggression post-transport, with no effect on water quality parameters (Vanderzwalmen *et al.* 2020).

Some participants fed their fishes twice a day, which along with the presence of substrate, the absence of water quality testing or regular water changes, provides potential for substrate to harbour waste products and a build-up of pathogenic bacteria. Over 50% of participants had live plants within their aquarium and 25% fed their fishes a diet of live food, both of which facilitate an additional opportunity for pathogens to enter the water system and be housed within the substrate. Therefore, there is an increasing need to understand further the advantages and also disadvantages of having substrate in an aquarium. The substrate samples that were returned by participants as part of the survey work in Chapter 3 may provide insight into the microbial communities living within UK home aquaria and forms part of a larger ongoing project. Analysis of these samples was beyond the scope of this thesis.

There are several limitations within this thesis and areas for future development. The experimental work in Chapter 2 explored the effects of substrate on fish behaviour. Water quality was tested to ensure that it was above the requirements of good husbandry. Additional water and substrate samples were taken for detailed water chemistry and microbiological analysis but there was not scope within the timescale of this thesis to analyse the results taken. Once these results have been analysed as part of another project, these data can hopefully be combined to provide a greater understanding of substrate impacts. One of the negative impacts of substrate that researchers have found is the changes to the microbiome, allowing pathogenic bacteria to accumulate, so had this been investigated, it would have given a further insight into the effects of substrate on home aquaria.

Only two fish species were investigated in Chapter 2 and only three different substrate types were considered. While they represent, as evidenced by the results of Chapter 3, the most popular fish and substrate types, it would be good to consider a greater range of species and substrates. Studies using bottom-dwelling species or those that access food by sifting through substrate, such as *Geophagus*, loaches or goldfish, are likely to give a greater insight to how substrate affects fish behaviour. The size of the simulated home aquaria was also quite small, larger home aquaria

may have allowed a greater number of individuals and/or fish species to be considered together, which may have provided different results. In Chapter 3, some very clear results were found in terms of the type of home aquaria that are the most common (i.e., tropical freshwater) and the prevalence of the use of substrate. The original aim was to obtain results from 200 participants, however, only 100 people responded to the advert and of those 56 surveys were returned. Future work may look to supplement this electronically to gain a more widespread insight into fish husbandry techniques used by UK fish-keepers.

In conclusion, the effects of substrate on fish behaviour and welfare remain under-researched. As most home aquarists add substrate to their tanks, more research is urgently required to determine whether substrate plays a beneficial or detrimental role within home aquaria. Further research is required, to gain a greater understanding of the ways in which aquarists maintain their home aquarium, why they include added features such as substrate and whether they have good welfare practices. There is also a need for greater education, to provide fish-keepers worldwide with information on tank substrate and how enrichment types may be affecting their fishes negatively or positively.

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Appendix A

Non-significant values from analysis of behaviours in Chapter 2.

Behaviour	Week*Feeding	Week*Substrate	Feeding*Substrate	Week*Feeding*Substrate
Escape Response	$F_{3,156}=0.603, p=0.614$	$F_{9,156}=5.03, p=0.871$	$F_{3,52}=2.108, p=0.110$	$F_{9,156}=0.561, p=0.827$
Interaction with Substrate	$F_{3,156}=1.330, p=0.267$	$F_{9,156}=4.30, p<0.001$	$F_{3,52}=4.320, p=0.009$	$F_{9,156}=0.890, p=0.536$
Foraging	$F_{3,156}=2.908, p<0.05$	$F_{9,156}=2.147, p<0.029$	$F_{3,52}=3.048, p=0.037$	$F_{9,156}=0.758, p=0.656$
Interaction with Enrichment	$F_{3,156}=1.500, p=0.217$	$F_{9,156}=1.273, p=0.256$	$F_{3,52}=2.770, P<0.05$	$F_{3,52}=0.500, p=0.684$
Aggression	$F_{3,162}=0.141, p=0.935$	$F_{9,162}=0.954, p=0.480$	$F_{3,54}=0.026, p=0.994$	$F_{3,54}=0.852, p=0.471$
Erratic Movement	$F_{1,52}=7.791, p<0.05$	$F_{3,52}=1.408, p>0.05$	$F_{3,52}=0.709, p=0.551$	$F_{3,52}=0.310, p=0.818$

Appendix B

Survey used in Chapter 3

Study Information Sheet: The Use of Substrate in Home Aquaria

You are invited to participate in a study investigating the use of substrate in home aquaria and its role in tank microbial communities. Please read this information prior to deciding whether you would like to take part and if you have any questions, please contact us using the details provided at the bottom of this page.

What is the purpose of the research? The purpose of this research is to help us understand the role substrate may play in microbial communities within a home aquarium and to understand the types of substrate used in home aquaria. Individuals are eligible to take part if they reside in the UK, own a home aquarium, and are aged 18+ years.

Do I have to take part? No, your participation is entirely voluntary, so it is completely your decision whether you participate or not. All questionnaire data and substrate samples are collected anonymously which means that once you have returned your questionnaire and substrate sample it cannot be withdrawn as your data will not be identifiable.

What will happen to me if I take part? The study will take about half an hour to complete, ideally as part of your routine tank cleaning. It involves completing a brief questionnaire about your home aquarium and then collecting a sample of substrate from your aquarium.

Study questionnaire: You will be asked to complete a short questionnaire (10-15 minutes). This will allow us to collect information on the type of aquarium you have, including how your aquarium is maintained. The details you provide will allow us to look at differences between home aquaria, water quality and substrate. After completing the questionnaire, you will be asked to take a sample of substrate from

your aquarium and send it back to us. This will allow us to analyse and determine different microbial communities present in your aquarium.

Substrate Sampling: Instructions for taking your substrate sample are provided at the end of the questionnaire. Please follow these instructions carefully. Substrate samples should be taken just before your usual tank cleaning and posted to us using the prepaid envelope provided as soon as possible, ideally within 24 hours of sampling.

What are the benefits of taking part? It is unlikely that you will experience any direct benefits from the research, but it will help us to develop an understanding of the type of substrates chosen by people for home aquaria and how these influence microbial communities, a topic which at present is under-researched. There is also the option to be entered into a prize draw for a £100 Amazon voucher. A summary of the overall results from the study will be available on request from the researchers once the study is complete in approximately 6-12 months' time.

Amazon gift voucher prize draw: All participants are welcome to enter a prize draw for a £100 Amazon gift voucher. This is your own choice and there is no requirement to do so. Entries are accepted on receipt of a completed questionnaire and substrate sample and require you to provide your email address on the last page of the questionnaire. Email addresses provided will only be used for the prize draw, will be detached from the questionnaire immediately on receipt and will not be kept or stored for any other purpose.

Are there any risks to taking part? The risks associated with this project are the same as for keeping home aquaria in general. There is a risk with electrical equipment and water, and also a minimal risk from zoonotic diseases. Please see the safety notice below which documents the risks assessed with this project and their mitigation measures.

SAFETY NOTICE!

The following is a list of safety precautions to be taken when gathering your sample.

- **TURN OFF ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT** - Ensure that all electrical appliances (pumps, lights, etc) are turned off at the main power supply before touching the tank water. (Remember to turn back on once complete for the safety of your fishes!).
- **CAREFULLY REMOVE BREAKABLES** - Take care when removing any breakable objects (glass lids) and place them securely on a safe surface before carefully replacing after sampling.
- **WASH HANDS** - There is a small risk of *Mycobacterium* infection from keeping a fish aquarium, and other pathogenic bacteria may also be present in the water. You should always wash hands thoroughly after contact with aquarium water to avoid bacteria transmission. These infections are more likely if you have broken skin or cuts on your hands or arms or are immunocompromised. Further information on the risks of keeping home aquaria can be found at <https://ornamentalfish.org/fish-keeper/useful-information/> in the Guidance section on 'Hygiene tips to stop disease transfer'. You are provided with a pair of nitrile gloves to take the substrate sample; these are hypo-allergenic but please do not use if you have an allergy to nitrile gloves. If you normally use gloves for cleaning your tank then these can be used instead as long as they are clean. Even though gloves are worn, please still wash your hands and any part of your skin that comes into contact with tank water thoroughly after sampling. If it would not normally be safe to put your hands into your aquarium during routine husbandry/cleaning (e.g. if your fish bite) then you should not take part in this study.

What will happen to my data? The data you provide will be anonymous and will be stored on password protected computers and/or external hard drives. While your substrate sample will be linked to your questionnaire with a unique identification number, no personal identifiable information will be collected. If a sample pack has

been sent to you in the post, no record has been kept of which sample pack number was sent to you and your address has not been stored. As stated above, if you wish to participate in the prize draw you will need to provide an email address but this will be kept completely separate from your data. The findings from this study will be written up as part of two M.Res. theses, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars.

Who organised, funded and approved the research? This research has been organised by Louise Ross and Michael Crossan, two M.Res. Students at the University of the West of Scotland. The work is in part funded by Mars Petcare UK. This study has been approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland and the Mars Research Review Board.

Who can I contact for more information?

Louise Ross, Research Masters Student

Email: [REDACTED]

Michael Crossan, Research Masters Student

Email: [REDACTED]

Prof. Katherine Sloman, Lead Supervisor

Email: [REDACTED]

If you have any concerns and you would like to contact someone at the University of the West of Scotland who knows about the study but is not directly involved, please contact: [REDACTED]

SURVEY

Before completing the survey and taking a substrate sample please read the Study Information Sheet above.

By completing the questionnaire and returning a substrate sample you are confirming that:

(i) I have read the study information sheet provided to me and consent to participate in this research.

(ii) In particular, I have read the Safety Notice above and understand the risks associated with taking a substrate sample and will take necessary precautions.

(iii) I understand that my data will be collected anonymously so once I have returned the questionnaire and substrate sample I will not be able to withdraw my data.

(iv) I am 18+ years old.

Survey on the Use of Substrate in Home Aquaria

1) How many and what type/species of fishes do you keep in your aquarium?

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2) Is your aquarium freshwater or marine?

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3) Is your aquarium tropical or temperate/cold water?

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4) Please provide a description of your tank (e.g. what type of material is it made from, is it a particular brand, what are its dimensions?).

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5) How much water do you have in your tank regularly (e.g. depth of water or volume)? How often do you carry out full and/or partial water changes?

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6) Do you use water treatments or water conditioners (e.g. Stress Coat) to treat the water? If yes, what type of treatment and how often?

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7) Do you test your aquarium water for water quality parameters (e.g. pH, ammonia)? If yes, how do you carry out these tests and how often? If you are able to provide here a pH value for your tank at the time you took the substrate sample that would be beneficial.

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8) Do you use substrate in the bottom of the tank? If yes, how deep is the layer of substrate? Do you clean the substrate and if so how often?

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9) If you do have substrate in the bottom of the tank, why do you choose to add substrate?

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10) Do you have additional enrichment in your aquarium (i.e. plants, ornaments)? If yes, what type of enrichment and what is it made of?

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11) How often and approximately how much do you feed your fish? What type of food do you use and how do you feed your fish (i.e. scattered on top of water, placed on ornaments or plants)?

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Amazon gift voucher prize draw

If you would like to be entered into a prize draw for the chance to win a £100 Amazon gift voucher, please provide your email address here. Entry into the draw is dependent on receipt of a completed questionnaire and substrate sample.

Email:

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Note: To ensure your data remain anonymous, this sheet will be removed on receipt of your questionnaire by UWS and will remain separate from that point forward. Email addresses provided will only be used by UWS for the purpose of the prize draw which will occur once the study is complete and will then be destroyed.

Instructions for Taking Substrate Sample

To collect your substrate sample please follow these steps carefully. Please make sure you have read the Safety Notice above.

Note: Please take your substrate sample before routine tank cleaning. Ideally substrate samples should be returned within 24 hours of the sample being taken.

1. Wash and dry hands thoroughly.
2. Turn off any electricals within the tank (e.g. pump, heater etc) to avoid risk of electrocution.
3. To prevent bacterial contamination of the sample with bacteria from your hands, please use either the nitrile gloves provided or, if you prefer, gloves that you would normally use for cleaning your tank to take the sample. Please put the gloves on before removing the sample tube from the plastic bag and taking the sample so that you do not contaminate the tube by touching it with bare hands.
4. Using the plastic tube provided please scoop up a sample of your substrate so that the tube is no more than half full. We only need a small amount of substrate; filling to the 5 or 10 ml line on the tube would be sufficient. The substrate should remain wet but please drain off any additional water so that there are no leaks during transport. Please try to avoid collecting food remains and fish waste with the substrate sample where possible.
5. Replace the lid on the tube, ensuring it is properly sealed. Remove one piece of absorbent paper from the sample bag and use it to dry the outside of the tube. Attach the label, writing the date and time of the sample collection **in pencil** on the label.
6. Return the sealed sample tube to the plastic bag along with the remaining piece of dry absorbent paper and seal the bag. Nitrile gloves can be rinsed and placed into general waste or you can return them in the plastic bag with the sample and we will dispose of them for you. Place the sealed bag into the return envelope provided, along with the completed questionnaire and information sheet.

7. Wash and dry hands thoroughly.
8. Turn tank electricals back on and ensure they are working.
9. Please post your prepaid return envelope to us as soon as possible, ideally within 24 h of taking the sample. [N.B. This was changed on surveys which could be returned to store].